

HARVARD COLLEGE

SENIOR THESIS

Searching for 55 Cancri g:
A Hardware-to-Planet Approach

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Abstract

Humanity’s search for exoplanets has led to the discovery of rich and complex planetary systems unlike our own. With its five known planets and the tantalizing hint of more, 55 Cancri is one such system. This thesis takes a “hardware-to-planet” approach in order to search for 55 Cnc g – a sixth planet in the system – by means of the radial velocity (RV) method. This approach required an interdisciplinary effort that involved hardware, software, and analysis projects.

I envisioned using the MINERVA observatory (Mt.Hopkins, AZ) to obtain new 55 Cnc radial velocity data. Thus, at the instrumentation level, I set out to help expedite MINERVA’s ability to fulfill its primary science goal of becoming a dedicated Doppler-based detection facility. Through a collaborative effort, I helped install a new generation of fibers that transmit light from the telescopes to the spectrograph, and improved the throughput of the old set of fibers by a factor of ~ 10 . I also helped repair the observatory from an unexpected mechanical failure, and carried out a two-stage snow-protection plan to prevent the failure from happening again. At the software level, I assessed the feasibility of incorporating a 22-parameter model into the MINERVA Doppler reduction pipeline to better characterize its instrumental profile. I found that the model is extremely sensitive to initial conditions, and an automated algorithm that independently fine-tunes the initial guess for each parameter is necessary to achieve convergence.

Ultimately, delays due to the fiber installation and the unexpected mechanical failure prevented me from obtaining original 55 Cnc data with MINERVA. Nonetheless, this thesis uses 1602 high precision radial velocity observations of 55 Cancri, including 200 new RVs from the 2017 Keck/HIRES data release, to present an updated study of the system. I employ the EXOFASTv2 IDL software package (Eastman et al., in prep) to obtain a 5-planet radial velocity model of the system, as well as its stellar and planetary parameter estimates and uncertainties. The derived parameters are consistent with literature values within 2σ . Fitting the 5-planet fit residuals with EXOFAST (Eastman et al., 2013) yields a significant signal in the periodogram, which could correspond to a sixth planet with a period $P = 1736_{-15}^{+16}$ days, a RV semi-amplitude $K = 3.126_{-0.25}^{+0.28}$ m s⁻¹, and a semi-major axis $a = 2.795_{-0.018}^{+0.019}$ AU. A period of ~ 1736 days places planet g in a 3:1 mean motion resonance (MMR) with planet d. Although dynamical stability analyses in the published literature allow such a planet, the signal could also stem from systematic errors such as stellar activity cycles. Therefore, I conclude this thesis by summarizing additional analysis that must be carried out before rejecting or confirming the existence of 55 Cnc g.

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Chapter 1

A HISTORY OF EXOPLANET SCIENCE, FROM ANCIENT GREECE TO MINERVA

1.1 Introduction: A Millennial Search for Exoplanets

Although all the confirmed discoveries of exoplanets have occurred in the last three decades, humans have been pondering about their existence for over two millennia.¹ The earliest and most explicit reference comes from the Greek philosopher and atomist Epicurus (341 - 271 BC), who in a letter to another philosopher of the time said “There are infinite worlds both like and unlike this world of ours. For the atoms being infinite in number, as was already proven, ... so that there nowhere exists an obstacle to the infinite number of worlds” (Epicurus, 305 BC). Two thousand years later, the late seventeenth century scientist Christiaan Huygens (1629 - 1695) theorized in his book *Cosmotheoros* that “We are far from observing planets around the stars because they are very faint, and because their orbits are indistinguishable from the observed spot of starlight” (Huygens, 1762). Lastly, in 1952 Russian astronomer Otto Struve speculated that extra solar planets could be discovered via high-precision stellar radial velocity work (Struve, 1952).

Determining which was the first exoplanet detection is a subject of contentious debate.

¹See NASA’s Planet Quest Historic Time line at <https://www.nasa.gov/externalflash/PQTimeline/>

In 1988, Campbell et al. announced the *potential* discovery of an exoplanet orbiting γ Cephei, which they detected via Doppler spectroscopy. Doppler spectroscopy, or the radial velocity (RV) method, consists of measuring the “wobble” of a host star due to the presence of an orbiting planet, which manifests itself in the Doppler shift of the stellar spectrum. Because Campbell et al.’s (1988) detection wasn’t confirmed until 2003 (Hatzes et al., 2003), it is considered the first exoplanet detection, but only on hindsight. A similar tale is that of HD 114762b, detected in 1989 by Latham et al. and initially thought to be a brown dwarf due to its large mass ($\sim 11 M_{\text{Jup}}$). Most astronomers attribute the first discovery of an exoplanet to Wolszczan & Frail (1992), who utilized radio data and the pulsar timing method to detect two planets around the pulsar PSR B1257+12.² In 1995, Mayor & Queloz found the first exoplanet around a main-sequence star. Using precise Doppler spectroscopy, they detected a $0.42 \pm 0.02 M_{\text{Jup}}$ planet orbiting the Sun-like star 51 Pegasi. Shortly thereafter, Marcy & Butler (1996), and a joint team from the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics (CfA), the High Altitude Observatory, and Pennsylvania State University confirmed the discovery of 51 Pegasi b. As will become apparent in Section 1.4.2, Marcy & Butler continued to make important contributions to the development of Doppler spectroscopy, discovering more than half of the exoplanets known prior to the launch of NASA’s *Kepler* mission in 2009 (Borucki et al., 2009).

Besides Doppler spectroscopy, other exoplanet detection methods have contributed significantly to the growth of exoplanet science. With the transit method, for example, astronomers detect exoplanets by measuring the decrease in flux generated by a planet as it passes in front of its host star. This method was first used by Charbonneau et al. (2000) & Henry (2000) to detect a $1.27 \pm 0.02 R_{\text{Jup}}$ planet orbiting HD 209458, which was known from RV measurements to have a planetary mass companion. According to the NASA Exoplanet Archive, astronomers have discovered over 3000 exoplanets via transiting events.³ As early as 2012, *Kepler* had increased the number of exoplanet candidates

²To date, these are the only two exoplanets discovered around pulsars.

³Visit <http://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/docs/countsdetail.html> for more Exoplanet statistics

by over a factor of five (Traub, 2012). Additionally, ground-based transit surveys, such as HAT (Bakos et al., 2004), TrES (Alonso et al., 2004), WASP (Christian et al., 2006), and KELT (Pepper et al., 2007), have also been instrumental toward the detection of new worlds, and have enabled exoplanet scientists to move beyond discovery and into studies pertaining to the statistics and evolution of planetary populations (e.g., Howard et al., 2010; Cassan et al., 2012; Mordasini et al., 2012; Gaidos et al., 2016). Today, we understand that planets are abundant around GKM dwarf stars (Howard et al., 2012; Fressin et al., 2013), and that their occurrence rates increase with longer orbital periods and smaller planetary radii (e.g., Borucki, 2010; Traub, 2012). The diversity of exoplanet detections has also informed planet-formation theories, and contributed to the development of planet population synthesis models (Howe et al., 2014). There is still much to learn about the diversity, abundance and evolution of exoplanets. Luckily, we live in a Universe teeming with undiscovered worlds. Presently, the K2 mission is looking for more transiting candidates in the ecliptic plane. In future years, missions such as NASA’s Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS), set to launch in 2018, will monitor new and bright targets (Ricker et al., 2015). TESS is expected to find more than a thousand sub-Neptune sized planets, many of which will be similar in radius to the Earth. This all-sky survey will also explore planetary populations around M Dwarfs, the most abundant type of star in our galaxy (Dressing & Charbonneau, 2013).

Other modern detection techniques have made important contributions toward the discovery of exoplanets, and have promising futures. In microlensing, for example, a suitable exoplanet acts as an additional gravitational lens, leaving characteristic (and measurable) signatures in the light curve of the background star (Mao & Paczynski, 1991; Gould & Loeb, 1992). Combined with parallax and stellar mass of the host star, microlensing can give us the mass of the detected exoplanet. Microlensing is capable of finding the furthest planets amongst the currently available methods (including low-mass planets), thereby probing entirely different planetary populations. The first microlensing exoplanet detection was

made by Bond et al. (2004), and ~ 34 more have been discovered since.⁴ One additional exoplanet detection method is direct imaging, wherein astronomers may photograph an exoplanet (in optical or infra-red wavelengths) while blocking the host star's light with a high-contrast coronagraph. Although direct imaging does not provide masses, and only gives a rough estimate of the planets radius, it has begun to yield luminosities and spectroscopic information of the planet, which are particularly exciting for the study of exoplanet atmospheres. The first exoplanets detected via direct imaging were Fomalhaut b (Kalas et al., 2008), and the four planets around HR 8799 (Mordasini et al., 2012). About 40 more exoplanets have been detected with this method.⁵

The future of microlensing and direct imaging is both promising and exciting. The European Space Agency's *Gaia* Mission (Lindegren et al., 2008), launched in 2013, will measure the parallaxes of one billion stars in our Galaxy and throughout the Local Group to unprecedented precision (see de Bruijne et al. (2014) for more information). Microlensing events detected by KMTNet (Shvartzvald et al., 2015), combined with parallax data obtained with *Gaia*, will allow for the measurement of the masses of new microlensing exoplanets. Additionally, thousands of exoplanets will be found with NASA's WFIRST-AFTA microlensing mission (Yee et al., 2014). In the case of direct imaging, a state-of-the-art 10^{-9} contrast coronagraph on-board NASA's JWST mission, MIRI, will demonstrate the technological capabilities of this detection method, and has an expected yield of ~ 21 new planets (Stapelfeldt et al., 2014).

Among this collection of detection methods and future missions, Doppler spectroscopy plays a central role: it is the prevalent method for measuring planetary masses. Coupled with information on a planet's radius (obtained via the transit method), RV measurements allow us to obtain the bulk densities of exoplanets - crucial information for determining, for example, whether a planet is rocky and capable of sustaining life as we know it on Earth (Marcy et al., 2014). What is more, RV follow-up of *Kepler* candidates provides

⁴NASA Exoplanet Archive, <http://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu>

⁵NASA Exoplanet Archive, <http://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu>

confirmation of the planetary nature of a transit signal. As TESS data becomes available in the next few years, the demand for RV follow-up will increase significantly (Plavchan et al., 2015). As a result, Doppler-based facilities dedicated to RV characterization will be essential for studies of planetary formation, exoplanet populations, and the habitability of new-found worlds. The Miniature Exoplanet Radial Velocity Array (MINERVA) is one such facility, and is the subject of Section 1.2.

1.2 MINERVA

1.2.1 Motivation, and an Outline for this Thesis

Prior to the launch of the *Kepler* mission in 2009, ground-based transit and RV surveys had already discovered about 400 planets orbiting nearby targets. These RV detections increased our understanding of the wide range of masses, radii, and internal structures of exoplanets, seeing as they surpassed the diversity of the Solar System (e.g., Cosentino et al., 2012; Bonfils, X. et al., 2013; Foreman-Mackey et al., 2014). A particularly interesting new class of planets had masses and radii intermediate to the terrestrial planets and the ice-giants, Neptune and Uranus, – they were named “super-Earths” (e.g., Crane et al., 2010; Landolt, 1992; Riddle et al., 2014). Pre-*Kepler* RV detections also revealed correlations between stellar properties and planetary occurrence (e.g., Fischer & Valenti, 2005; Johnson et al., 2010). Additionally, Howard et al. (2010) found that 23% of Sun-like stars harbor an Earth-mass planet, an exciting statistical result from the perspective of low-mass exoplanet surveys.

Consistent with early ground-based transit and RV surveys, the thousands of *Kepler* exoplanet discoveries have reinforced the inverse relation between planetary size and planetary occurrence (see Section 1.1). Despite uncertainties in this trend toward the smallest detected planets, statistical evidence suggests that planets smaller than $4 R_{\oplus}$ are more abundant than larger ones in our galaxy (Howard et al., 2010). In particular, Fressin et al.

(2013) estimated the occurrence of Earth-sized planets around Sun-like stars to range between 10 and 15%. *Kepler* detections have also shown us that terrestrial planets orbiting Main Sequence stars are very common, and may be the most abundant if one considers recent planet occurrence estimates around M dwarfs, the most common type of star in the Milky Way. Specifically, Dressing & Charbonneau (2013) found that the occurrence rate of $0.5 - 4 R_{\oplus}$ with $P \leq 50$ days is $0.90_{-0.03}^{+0.04}$ planets per star. Assuming these statistical results translate to the Solar Neighborhood, it is very likely that we have yet to detect a myriad of terrestrial-mass and super-Earths within ~ 10 pc from the Solar System.

RV surveys have been suggested as a better method for discovering new nearby exoplanets, given that detection probability is a lot less sensitive to orbital inclination (Swift et al., 2015). Nonetheless, RV surveys possess challenges of their own. The detection of small planets requires RV errors of 1 m s^{-1} or less, below the current precision of most instruments. What is more, a RV survey would require extremely high cadence to combat stellar jitter (Swift et al., 2015). The high demand for telescope time on the few instruments capable of achieving the required RV precision (e.g., HARPS-N on the ESO, HIRES on Keck) makes it unfeasible to carry out such a survey with existing observatories.

The Miniature Radial Velocity Array (MINERVA) was built in order to address the need for a dedicated Doppler-based observatory capable of characterizing the planetary masses of small planets – in particular, super-Earths – in the Solar Neighborhood. This facility has the potential to locate and characterize dozens of planets within ~ 20 pc of the Earth (Swift et al., 2015), and will ultimately inform the target lists of space-based missions designed to discover the first Earth 2.0 (e.g. TESS, MIRI on-board JWST; see Section 1.1 for more details). Nonetheless, work in multiple fronts remains to be done before MINERVA can begin exploring the skies.

With this context in mind, the *underlying* goal of my thesis consisted of expediting MINERVA’s ability to fulfill its primary science goal – becoming a dedicated Doppler-based detection facility of small planets orbiting stars in the Solar Neighborhood. I tackled

this goal from three different fronts. Firstly, at the instrumentation level, I contributed to the installation of the science fibers – which are responsible for transporting star light from the telescopes to the spectrograph –, as well as the overall improvement and maintenance of the observatory. Secondly, at the software level, I assessed the feasibility of incorporating a 22-parameter spectral model into MINERVA’s Doppler-shift-extraction pipeline. Given that this model may more accurately describe the instrumental profile (IP) of MINERVA in a non-degenerate manner, its integration into the pipeline has the potential to improve the RV precision of the array. Lastly, I contributed to the development of EXOFASTv2, the second version of an IDL software package that MINERVA (and many others) will use in order to fit RV curves and quantify a planetary system’s parameter values and uncertainties. In helping to develop EXOFASTv2, I became the first person to use the software to fit a multi-planetary system – 55 Cancri – using RV data only.⁶ 55 Cancri is a rich and complex system located about 13 pc from the Earth. I chose 55 Cancri from the MINERVA target list (~ 193 targets) due to its brightness, observability from the MINERVA site between 2016 November and 2017 January, and the tantalizing hint of a sixth planet in the literature (e.g., Fischer et al., 2008; Raymond et al., 2008). Thus, searching for 55 Cancri g became the *driving* goal of my thesis.

Integrating all of the above projects is the philosophy of my thesis, which consists of improving my understanding of the entire process through which photons that fall on the telescope primary “become” RV data points, eventually informing a RV model. Through the MINERVA hardware projects, I became aware of the instrumentation requirements needed to collect photons from a star, and consequently generate a raw stellar spectrum. Through the MINERVA software project, I engaged with the pipeline in charge of modeling the raw stellar spectrum and measuring a redshift that will eventually become a RV datum. Lastly, by using EXOFASTv2 to search for 55 Cancri g, I learned how to use RV data to model RV curves of multi-planetary systems. Given my career aspiration to design and

⁶EXOFASTv2 has already been used to fit multi-planetary systems using both transit and RV data. See e.g., Rodriguez et al. (2017).

build the next generation of astronomical instruments, I believe that this “hardware-to-planet” philosophy will accompany me throughout the rest of my career.

Chapter 1 provides an overview of the MINERVA hardware (§1.2.3), with a particular focus on the instrumental components that will allow MINERVA to fulfill its primary science goal. Specifically, In Sections 1.3.1 and 1.3.2, I discuss the two trips adviser Jason Eastman and I took to Mt.Hopkins, AZ, in order to install the next generation of fibers and fix the telescope after unexpected damages. I present an overview of MINERVA’s present Doppler pipeline in Section 1.2.5. Section 1.4.3 contrasts the present 7-parameter spectral model against the 22-parameter experimental model. In concluding the first chapter, Section 1.4.5 describes the modifications made to the Doppler pipeline code in order to accommodate the experimental model, and assess the feasibility of implementing it permanently.

Chapter 2 provides a connection between science light acquisition, redshift deduction, and the derivation of a planetary system’s parameters. I begin with a detailed derivation of the RV equation in Section 2.1.1. Section 2.2 explains the EXOFAST methodology and RV model parametrization, including a description of *how* the software package utilizes the RV equation to model single-planet systems. Chapter 3 begins with a description of EXOFASTv2 in contrast to its predecessor. In Section 3.3, I use 1602 PRV observations from five observatories (Lick, Keck, Hobby-Eberly Telescope (HET), Observatoire de Haute-Provence (OHP), and Harlan J. Smith Telescope (HJST)) to characterize the 55 Cancri system (55 Cnc hereafter). Section 3.1 recounts the detection history and characteristics of 55 Cnc, as well as our motivations for choosing it. In Section 3.3.3, I describe the *potential* detection of 55 Cnc g, and suggest future studies that are necessary to determine whether this is in fact a new planet. I conclude with a summary of our results, and a glimpse into the future of MINERVA and EXOFAST.

1.2.2 MINERVA’s Science Goals

MINERVA will search for small planets orbiting bright stars ($V \lesssim 8$) in our Solar Neighborhood, with a particular interest in super-Earths lying within their respective “Habitable Zones”. MINERVA is located at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory (FLWO) on Mt. Hopkins in the outskirts of Amado, AZ, at a latitude of $31^{\circ}40'49.4''$ N, a longitude of $110^{\circ}52'44.6''$ W, and an elevation of 2400 m (7816 ft). MINERVA is one of five observing facilities located in the Mt.Hopkins Ridge, along with HATNet, the 1.5 m (60”) and 1.2 m (48”) Tillinghast reflectors, and the decommissioned PAIRITEL (Fig 1.1b). MINERVA will carry out a three-year-long RV survey of bright solar-type stars (Swift et al., 2015). The *NASA/UC* η_{\oplus} Survey conducted using the HIRES spectrograph at Keck Observatory serves as the foundation for the MINERVA target list. The η_{\oplus} Survey by the California Planet Search (CPS) group searched for low-mass planets ($\sim 3 - 30M_{\oplus}$) orbiting 230 nearby GKM stars (Howard et al., 2009). Swift et al. (2015) built the final target list considering the location of the array (southern Arizona), the precision necessary to detect planets with $M_p \sin i \sim 3M_{\oplus}$ over three years, the length of nights ($\gtrsim 6.5$ hours), weather conditions (~ 271 nights/year will have a median seeing of 1.2”) and a 25 s telescope slew and source acquisition time. I chose 55 Cnc from this target list.

Howard et al.’s (2010) statistical results helped estimate the projected yield of exoplanets from the final target list of MINERVA, which in turn dictated the minimum aperture required for the array. Swift et al. (2015) carried out simulations to determine the minimum effective aperture of MINERVA. The simulations assumed a RV precision limit of 0.8 m s^{-1} and used a photon noise model. Additionally, they accounted for stellar jitter, target observability and weather loss predictions based on historical records for southern Arizona. The final yield result from the simulations indicated that an effective aperture of 1.4 m would allow for the observation of the 82 brightest stars in the η_{\oplus} Survey, with a mean yield of 15 ± 4 planets with amplitudes between 0.8 m s^{-1} and 3 m s^{-1} . In light of the simulation results, MINERVA was designed around the use of four 0.7 m telescopes.

(a) Background: the four MINERVA telescopes in their respective “Aqawan” (clam-like) domes. Foreground: MINERVA Red inside its round-shaped dome.

(b) Locations of all astronomical facilities at the Mt. Hopkins Ridge, with MINERVA at the bottom left. The MINERVA telescopes are installed on the site of the decommissioned FLWO 10 m gamma-ray telescope. The 6.5 m Multiple Mirror Telescope (MMT) is located toward the NW of MINERVA (not depicted). Image taken from Swift et al. (2015).

Figure 1.1: Location and visual of the MINERVA site and telescopes.

MINERVA’s telescopes and other hardware are the focus of the next section.

1.2.3 Hardware

1.2.3.1 Telescopes

MINERVA consists of four PlaneWave CDK-700 0.7-m altitude/azimuth telescopes (1.4 m effective aperture). These are corrected Dall-Kirkham telescopes consisting of an elliptical primary mirror, a spherical secondary mirror, and a lens group in front of the focal point, which improves off-axis image quality (Swift et al., 2015). Each CDK-700 telescope also has dual Nasmyth ports accessed via a rotating tertiary mirror. The optical system has a focal length $f = 4540$ mm and f -number 6.5. Each telescope is equipped with a wide-field CCD camera on one of its two Nasmyth ports. Three of the telescopes use Andor iKON-L cameras, with 2048×2048 square $13.5 \mu\text{m}$ pixels for a total chip size of 27.6 mm covering a $20.9'$ field. A fourth telescope houses an Apogee Aspen CG230 camera with 2048×2048 square $15 \mu\text{m}$ pixels corresponding to a chip size of 30.7 mm and a $23.2'$ FOV. All the Andor cameras mate to filter wheels through a custom adaptor plate, shown in Fig. 1.2. Three of the MINERVA telescopes use AFW50-7s filter wheels, while the fourth telescope uses a custom double filter wheel made up of two AFW50-10s wheels mounted contiguously. The filters available to the MINERVA system include: the Johnson B , V , R , I ; and the second generation Sloan g' , r' , i' , and z' .

Two direct-drive electromagnetic motors control the telescope pointing, which has an accuracy of $10''$ RMS, and a tracking accuracy of $1''$ over three minutes. Slew time between any two points in the sky is less than 10 seconds. Each of the four telescopes rests on an individual concrete pier 36 inches in diameter and 5 feet in height.

There are several advantages to using multiple telescopes over a single one. In particular, single dish telescopes with apertures greater than ~ 3 m have relatively low duty cycles for bright targets, seeing as exposure times are considerably shorter than read-out, slewing and source-acquisition times. In contrast, early radial-velocity searches with smaller apertures

Figure 1.2: Optical configuration of one of the Nasmyth port housing an Andor iKON-L CCD camera used for precision photometry. The custom adaptor plate is shown on the right. Image taken from Swift et al. (2015).

— such as that of Baranne et al. (1996) using ELODIE on the 1.93 m OHP telescope — have proved effective and efficient. Indeed, smaller telescopes with fast slew speed facilitate the high cadence requirement of a RV survey with the goals of MINERVA. An array of four 0.7 m telescopes with a 1.4 m effective aperture is also cheaper than a single telescope with equivalent light-collecting capacity. Swift et al. (2015) showed that, while telescope cost scales (roughly) linearly with aperture size, there is a significant price surge between the largest commercial telescopes (about 1 m in diameter) and somewhat larger professional telescopes (Fig. 1.3). The four commercial telescopes used for MINERVA will feed its spectrograph the same amount of photons as would a larger, $5\times$ more expensive telescope with an effective aperture of 1.4 m. The fact that the telescopes were purchased off-the-shelf and with complete control software offsets the inherent complexities of coordinating a telescope array.

In lieu of traditional domes, two Aqawans house four MINERVA telescopes (see Figure

Figure 1.3: Cost vs. aperture for three different telescope types. The red curve, representing cost of amateur telescope as a function of aperture, suggests a linear relationship. A price surge at ~ 1 m aperture is shown at the transition boundary (*purple*) between amateur telescopes (*red*) and professional telescopes (*blue*). The bottom (*green*) line shows the cost and effective aperture for different amounts of CDK-700 0.7 m telescopes.

1.1b).⁷ This type of enclosure was designed by Las Cumbres Observatory Global Telescope (LCOGT) to facilitate remote, robotic operation of their 0.4 m telescopes (Brown, 2013). Swift et al. (2015) purchased two custom-built (upscaled) Aqawans, each of which can accommodate two CDK-700 telescopes. The clam-like design minimizes dome-seeing effects by providing full sky access, and eliminates the need for dome-slit positioning automation. Each enclosure also includes a temperature and humidity sensor, fans to promote temperature stabilization, and surveillance cameras with 360° coverage.

Two motors⁸ inside each Aqawan are connected to two lateral poles via U-joints. The poles rotate a sprocket to roll and unroll two chains. The chains open and close the shutters (Fig. 1.4). Six limit switches installed inside each Aqawan stop the motor before

⁷Aqawan means to “to be dry” in Chumash native American.

⁸The motor power and gear ratio were also increased to handle heavier roof panels. Specifically, the Aqawan receives 208V/30A three phase power, which is converted to 24V DC power internally (Swift et al., 2015).

the shutters touch the ground, or each other when closing (but see Section 1.3.2).

Figure 1.4: 3D CAD model of the MINERVA Aqawans, with important components labeled.

During a trip to MINERVA on November 2016 (see Section 1.2.3.2), we installed heating strips along the edge of the Aqawan shutters in order to melt ice and snow that could otherwise fall into the telescopes upon opening the enclosures (Fig. 1.4,1.5). These heating strips prevent the domes from freezing shut (or open). The Aqawan firmware, software (§1.2.5), and added uninterruptible power supply (UPS) are designed such that the enclosures can close automatically in the face of inclement weather or unexpected power and connectivity failures (Swift et al., 2015). Nonetheless, other circumstances may lead to the failure of the Aqawan enclosures. In Section 1.3.2, we explain an additional failure mode of the Aqawans, and describe the instrumental upgrades we carried out in order to address it.

(a) Half-open Aqawan is depicted midway through the installation of a heater strip (black wavy cable) along the roof.

(b) Fully installed heater strip runs along the edge of the entire Aqawan, a portion of which is depicted here.

Figure 1.5: Stage 1 of the MINERVA snow protection plan.

1.2.3.2 Fiber-Optic Cables and KiwiSpec

Astronomical light collected by each of the 0.7 m telescopes is passed to fibers through the second Nasmyth port, which houses a fiber coupling system consisting of a fiber acquisition unit (FAU). The FAU was custom-built for MINERVA and is described in detail in Bottom et al. (2014). Figures 1.6a and 1.6b show a picture and a ray-trace illustration of the FAU optical components. As the telescope beam enters the FAU, a 0.98/0.02 beam splitter directs 98% of the light onto the fiber tip and reflects 2% of the beam onto an SBIG ST-i guide camera with a V-band filter. In order to center the star on the fiber tip, the fiber is backlit from the spectrograph end. Although 98% of the backlight is sent out to the telescope beam, the remaining 2% is reflected onto a corner cube, which consequently sends the light back to the guider camera. Thus, back illumination results in the imaging of the fiber tip onto the detector at the precise location where we need to put the star.

Starlight collected by the four CDK-700 telescopes feeds MINERVA’s stabilized spectrograph, KiwiSpec, via fiber optic cables. There have been two generations of science fibers on MINERVA, the first of which we installed on December, 2015 (before the beginning of this thesis). These first-generation science fibers, built by CeramOptec, have $50\ \mu\text{m}$ octagonal cores – which are superior spatial scramblers in comparison to circular fibers (Fig 1.7a)– and $330\ \mu\text{m}$ claddings with a lower refractive index to guarantee total internal reflection (TIR). See Figure 1.8 for a diagram of these fibers. This first generation has significant disadvantages, some of which I will mention here. First, the relatively large cladding size of each of the fibers prohibits their direct interface with KiwiSpec. In particular, the fiber spacing at the spectrograph end requires $220\ \mu\text{m}$ claddings. In turn, butt-coupled connectors (Fig. 1.7b) are needed to attach the $330\ \mu\text{m}$ cladding fibers to $220\ \mu\text{m}$ cladding fibers, which can interface with the spectrograph. Butt-coupled connectors align in order to bring specially prepared ends of two fiber optic cables in contact. The principal light losses of these connectors originate from lateral and longitudinal misalignment of the butt-coupled fibers, as well as reflection losses due to an index of refraction

(a) The MINERVA FAU mounted on one of two Nasmyth ports of a CDK700 telescope. The fiber pictured in the image corresponds to the first generation.

(b) Ray-trace analysis of the FAU. The achromatic lens and corner cube across the beam splitter (pellicle) allow for the fiber tip to be imaged onto the SBIG ST-i guide cam upon upon back-illumination.

Figure 1.6: Visual and optical overview of the MINERVA fiber acquisition unit (FAU). Images taken from Swift et al. (2015).

mismatch imposed by the glass-to-air interface of the mated joint (see Figure 1.7b). In the case of MINERVA, we estimate a geometric loss of 25% from a 10 μm ferrule decentration at the butt-couple. A second disadvantage stems from a 10 μm gap filled with epoxy between the polyamide/acrylate buffer and the fiber ferrule, which distorts the ends of the fibers and translates into significant increases in focal ratio degradation (FRD). A final, and significant defect of these old fibers is their secondary cladding. The presence of a secondary cladding inside a fiber widens the light beam, and translates into a large IP with a variable halo, which is disastrous for PRV. We estimate that the butt-couple mismatch, reflective losses, and secondary cladding resulted in a 75% loss of light. While some of these effects were ameliorated by re-terminating these old fibers (§1.3.1), the MINERVA team ordered a second-generation of fibers, which were manufactured by Polymicro Technologies and delivered to Mt. Hopkins on 2016 November. In theory, these new fibers were designed to address all of the disadvantages of the old ones, as well as maximize light throughput. In practice, such was not the case (see §1.3.1 for details).

The science fibers attached to the four telescopes carry starlight onto the MINERVA spectrograph, KiwiSpec (Gibson et al., 2012). KiwiSpec was commissioned in December 2016. Prior to commissioning, the southeastern-most room of the MINERVA building (Fig. 1.1b) was converted into a class 100,000 clean room capable of housing the spectrograph in a temperature-stabilized environment (Fig. 1.9c).

KiwiSpec was designed and built by Kiwistar Optics of Industrial Research Limited, in New Zealand. The instrument is bench-mounted, compact (0.75 m \times 1.5 m) and therefore well-suited for small telescopes like MINERVA (Gibson et al., 2012). It has a resolving power of $R \approx 80,000$. KiwiSpec’s dispersers consist of an R4 echelle grating with 31.6 grooves per mm (for primary dispersion), and a high-efficiency volume phase holographic grating (VPH) based grism (for cross-dispersion). In addition, the spectrograph employs an off-the-shelf Hasselblad 150 mm focal length camera lens, and a 2k \times 2k e2v 42-40 CCD detector with 13.5 μm pixels. KiwiSpec covers the wavelength range from 420 nm to 660

(a) Depiction of output intensity distribution for different fiber shapes and illumination sources. The output of the octagonal fiber(left) is evenly scrambled, essentially decoupled from the shape and location of the input illumination. A standard circular fiber unevenly scrambles the light, as is shown on the right. Image taken from Halverson et al. (2015).

(b) Cylindrical ferrule butt-coupled connectors feature interference-fit alignment sleeves for robust fiber-to-fiber alignment. The glass-to-air gap between cylindrical ferrules becomes apparent in the middle of the image (shown in white). Source: <http://www.strantech.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/>

Figure 1.7: First-generation fibers: salient characteristics.

Figure 1.8: Diagram of a first generation fiber, as seen through a THORLABS Fiber Inspection Scope. The assembled fiber consists of: (1) an octagonal core; (2) a primary cladding (small light gray ring); (3) a secondary cladding (large dark gray circle); (4) epoxy (small, slightly darker ring around the secondary cladding); and (5) a (vignetted) ferrule (white ring surrounding parts (1)-(4)). This image was taken following re-termination, but before polishing the fiber (see Section 1.3.1).

nm over 51 echelle orders. Its primary and secondary collimating mirrors, as well as the echelle grating, sit inside a vacuum chamber, while the cross-disperser, camera and CCD are located outside. An exposure meter is installed near the entrance slit of KiwiSpec. Figure 1.9a shows a schematic diagram of KiwiSpec with its key optical components.⁹

In conjunction with the spectrograph, Kiwistar Optics developed software to communicate with the instrument’s electronic components and sensors, which include the CCD detector, exposure meter, iodine (I_2) stage, and thorium-argon lamp, as well as the pres-

⁹For a complete description of KiwiSpec’s optical design, refer to Gibson et al. (2012).

sure/vacuum pump, temperature, pressure and humidity sensors. The MINERVA user may use the software to construct a sequence of spectra to be observed (Gibson et al., 2012). The header of each spectra contains relevant values and positions of the instrumental components (e.g., temperature of the clean room and iodine cell position.). Figure 1.10 shows a raw KiwiSpec spectrum.

1.2.4 Photometry

As mentioned in Section 1.2.2, the primary science goal of MINERVA is to detect small planets in the Solar Neighborhood via the RV method. Seeing as the goals of my thesis align with the primary science goals of MINERVA, my description of the telescope array focuses on the instrumental characteristics that will enable it to generate RV measurements of nearby targets. Nonetheless, MINERVA has a secondary science goal, which consists of searching the transit windows of newly discovered super-Earths. For completeness, therefore, I will dedicate this section to describing the photometric capabilities that will allow MINERVA to fulfill its secondary science goals.

The transit of a $3R_{\oplus}$ planet around a Sun-like star ($0.8M_{\odot} \lesssim M_* \lesssim 1.2M_{\odot}$) produces a flux decrement in the order of one millimagnitude (mmag). Thus, 1 mmag represents a lower limit for the photometric precision that MINERVA must achieve. Swift et al. (2015) observed 16 Cyg AB ($V = 5.95$) – an η_{\oplus} target (Howard et al., 2009) – using one of the MINERVA telescopes in the first commissioning site of the array, Pasadena, CA – and found that the array can achieve sub-mmag precision on ~ 4 minute binning timescales. Additionally, The RMS of the unbinned photometry was of 2.7 mmag (Swift et al., 2015). Since the stability of the atmosphere in Mt. Hopkins is superior to that of the commissioning site, one can infer that MINERVA will be capable of achieving sub-mmag photometric precision.

MINERVA is designed to observe targets with apparent magnitude, $V_{\text{Mag}} \lesssim 8$, i.e., extremely bright stars. Therefore, in order to avoid CCD saturation over exposures longer

(a) 3D-CAD model of KiwiSpec featuring the main optical components described in the text. Image taken from (Gibson et al., 2012).

(b) Schematic representation showing the key optical components of KiwiSpec. Image taken from (Gibson et al., 2012).

(c) KiwiSpec sits inside a vacuum chamber within the MINERVA clean room. Adviser Jason Eastman for scale.

Figure 1.9: KiwiSpec graphics.

Figure 1.10: Fits file corresponding to a day-time spectrum taken with KiwiSpec and MINERVA (as seen on SAOImage DS9). The spectrum was obtained during 2016 January 20. Each of the four science fiber traces represents the input from one of the four MINERVA telescopes, as the zoomed-in panel (right) shows.

than a second, MINERVA relies on the defocusing technique. Once the telescope is pointed to the target field, it defocuses the camera such that the flux burden from the target is spread out over more pixels in the CCD. The benefits of this technique include the mitigation of photometric error contributions from pixel-to-pixel variations, and the increase in integration times (Swift et al., 2015). In order to remove systematics in the light curves of observed systems, each of the remaining telescopes in the array – i.e., those which are not observing the main target– can be simultaneously assigned to observe a comparison star in a nearby FOV. This section has been included with the purpose of outlining MINERVA’s photometric capabilities from a hardware point-of-view, and as such does not represent a thorough overview of the transit method. For more details, and an example of a planetary

system analyzed with MINERVA transit photometry, please refer to Swift et al. (2015).

1.2.5 Software

MINERVA is designed to be a completely robotic, autonomous telescope array. As a result, MINERVA requires a complex software architecture to carry out its science goals. Adviser Jason Eastman wrote the MINERVA Robotic Software (MRS) from scratch starting in early 2015.¹⁰ Six computers are in charge of operating MINERVA: MAIN, KIWISPEC-PC and TELCOM1-4. While MAIN uses Ubuntu 12.04.8 as its base operating system (OS), TELCOM1-4 and KIWISPEC-PC use Windows 7 Pro.¹¹

MAIN oversees the performance of the entire system and monitors meteorological conditions while coordinating operations of the array. `DomeControl.py` is the daemon in charge of determining whether the Aqawans should be open or closed. The program loops every fifteen seconds, obtains humidity, wind and cloud coverage information from one of four weather sensors, checks the queue for open/close commands from the system or its human users, and sends a “heartbeat” in the event that the Aqawans should remain open. If the daemon ceases to generate a heartbeat, the Aqawans will close and the system will be shut down, leaving everything in a safe state. In order of preference¹² the weather sensors used by `DomeControl.py` are the MEarth cloud sensor (located about 430m to the North and at a slightly higher elevation than MINERVA), Aurora (located on the roof of the MINERVA control building), HAT-Net (also on the Mt.Hopkins Ridge about 130m North) and MINERVA (also on the roof of the MINERVA building). MAIN is also responsible for the execution of high-level commands that, for example, take sky flats or orchestrate all four telescopes to point at the same star, begin guiding, and acquire a spectrum. Lastly, MAIN communicates directly with the system’s Power Distribution Units (PDU), allowing

¹⁰With some help along the years from students Brian Lin (University of Toronto), Samson Johnson (The Ohio State University), Thomas Beatty (Pennsylvania State University), and Maurice Wilson (Harvard University).

¹¹Ideally, the six computers would use the same OS. Unfortunately, the KIWISPEC software, PWI, and MaximDL are incompatible with Linux (Ubuntu), which is more reliable.

¹²The criteria for preference are better stability and reliability.

for automated error recovery.

Each of the four telescopes and their sub-mechanisms are run with a single computer of the same number, TELCOM1-4. TELCOM1-4 run the PlaneWave Interface 2.2.0.18 (PWI) and MaximDL Pro 5 for their respective telescopes. The PWI controls the focusers, rotators, M3 mirror and auxiliary hardware on each CDK700 telescope, and MaximDL controls the telescopes' CCDs and filter wheels. While the PWI hosts its own server (allowing for direct communication with MAIN), MaximDL is linked to MAIN via an external server. KIWISPEC-PC handles spectrograph operations and subsystems, including mechanisms such as the I₂ stage, and the back-light motor. An external server allows for communication between the spectrograph mechanisms and MAIN. Additionally, 16 sensors and a thermal control black box make up a thermal control loop that regulates the temperature inside the clean room, necessary to stabilize the spectrograph and achieve RV precision of 1 m s⁻¹.

1.3 Hardware Projects

1.3.1 Fiber Installation

In November 2016, adviser Jason Eastman and a group of six undergraduate and graduate students (including myself) traveled to the MINERVA site in order to install the new science fibers. We carefully routed the ~ 35 m science fibers, a calibration fiber, and a data fiber to each of the Aqawans.¹³ Fig. 1.11 depicts several stages of this process. Although we did not damage any of the fibers during installation (Figure 1.12), some mechanical challenges did arise. The science fibers have reinforced jackets at both ends, which results in them having a minimum bending radius of ~ 6 in (15 cm). The relatively large bending radius makes the fibers protrude significantly out of the FAU, leaving them susceptible to snagging. We came up with a short-term solution which consisted of passing the fibers through a T-

¹³These fibers were shorter so as to reduce light loss.

shaped foam protector (Fig. 1.13). We also moved the FAU to the Nasmyth port that most often faces the interior of the Aqawan, reducing the risk of someone snagging the fibers when entering the enclosure. Additionally, the anti-reflective (AR) coated glass (attached to the fiber tip) increased the fiber ferrule length, requiring us to enlarge the FAU interface in order to accommodate the new fiber.

Figure 1.11: The delicate fibers arrived to Mt. Hopkins as shown in panel (a). (b) We began by extending the fibers out of the MINERVA building, in order to prevent disastrous tangling. After coiling the two back-up fibers, we proceeded to carefully route the 50 m science fibers, a calibration fiber, and a data fiber to each of the Aqawans. Panel (c) shows the location at which the fibers leave the MINERVA building, and are routed through subterranean PVC pipes leading to the two Aqawans.

The second-generation fibers are different from the first-generation in meaningful ways. Four of the seven fibers will be used for science light acquisition. The three additional fibers are ready to be used as calibrators, but ultimately we would like to use them in additional

Figure 1.12: Illuminated fibers at the v-groove spectrograph interface. Since all seven fibers are illuminated, we are assured that none of them were damaged during installation.

(a) Side-view.

(b) Profile.

Figure 1.13: Interim solution for fiber-telescope interface protection consists of a foam cover. Two different angles evidence the T-shape of the foam.

telescopes to synthesize a 1.8 m effective aperture for MINERVA. Polymicro Technologies (PT) manufactured these new fibers, and FiberTech Optica (FTO) assembled them. PT is known to produce fibers with minimal FRD, and FTO has experience with astronomical

fibers and claim less than 5% increase in FRD following assembly. The fibers have $50\ \mu\text{m}$ octagonal cores and $110\ \mu\text{m}$ claddings. The smaller cladding diameters allow for the seven continuous fibers – *without* butt-couple connectors – to interface directly with KiwiSpec, and as such they were expected to eliminate significant loss. The seven-fiber end interfaces with KiwiSpec via a v-groove assembly, with an $n = 1.5$ slab of glass epoxied in front of it. The glass, which also has an AR coating, was meant to ameliorate reflection losses at the glass-to-air interface. FiberOptica originally quoted a 0.5% light loss at the fiber-spectrograph interface. It became evident upon fiber testing that the AR coated glass had come off the v-groove assembly, which resulted in a $\sim 2.3^\circ$ tilt in the light beam orientation as it entered KiwiSpec. In turn, this required us to machine a device to tilt the fiber ferrule by 3.5° in order for starlight to hit the spectrograph collimator perpendicularly. The tilt between AR coated glass and v-groove also resulted in an air/epoxy gap which introduced the reflection losses the AR coated glass was supposed to avoid, as well as a fringing pattern that is detrimental for PRV. FTO will fix the v-groove issue upon request.

The biggest motivation for obtaining a second fiber set was to eliminate the secondary cladding (Fig. 1.8). In order to accomplish this, PT built a customized fiber using an industrial process that was supposed to eliminate the secondary cladding. Instead, we believe that during fabrication the core was melted with the primary cladding, thereby creating a ring-shaped secondary cladding, and rendering these new fibers unusable for PRV. As aforementioned, secondary claddings produce IPs which have large halos and vary with seeing conditions.

One option for addressing this problem consists of fabricating an entirely new third fiber set which uses a pre-custom octagonal form with a core-to-cladding ratio of 1:1.3 (which fulfills the TIR requirement that the cladding be $10\times$ as long as the wavelength of starlight). We are still waiting on Polymicro to find out if this pre-custom ratio is in stock. This option would result in a 0.5-1.0 year delay. A second option consists of etching 1–3mm of the existing fiber with Hydrofluoric Acid (HFA) a meter away from the spectrograph

interface. Since the HFA will eat through the fiber buffer and introduce cracks in the cladding, this is a risky procedure that could cost us the entire assembly. While Polymicro technicians are experienced in HF etching, the procedure makes the fibers fragile and much more likely to break during assembly and routing through the conduits. A third option is fusion splicing the fiber about one meter away from the spectrograph interface. FTO has limited experience with this procedure, but has demonstrated 12% FRD losses in 300 μm fibers. Splicing has the risk of introducing phase distortions, which may increase FRD. The MINERVA team is currently discussing which of these options to pursue.

As an interim solution, MINERVA has reverted to using the first-generation fiber set, which we re-installed in 2016 November. During our second trip to MINERVA (2017 February) we re-terminated these old fibers to address their poor FRD performance, and improve their throughput. While we cannot do much about the fiber's intrinsic FRD, we re-terminated the fibers in order to minimize phase distortions caused by the epoxy glue. Although in principle this process should reduce the fibers' FRD, we have yet to quantify their improvement. Adviser Jason Eastman carried out preliminary tests using day-time spectra, and found that re-termination resulted in a light throughput increase of about a factor of ten (Fig. 1.15). These results, while promising, are preliminary. On-going fiber testing with night-time spectra will give the MINERVA team a better idea of the impact of re-termination. I outline the main aspects of the re-termination process in Figure 1.14.

1.3.2 Aqawanpocalypse

In the early morning of 2017 January 26, MINERVA suffered a critical hardware failure, which froze the Aqawans in a half-open position. Significant snow accumulation ($\gtrsim 8$ in) around the enclosures allowed for the Aqawans to open far enough to rest on the snow, but did not trigger their respective limit switches. Without engaging the limits, the motors kept rotating, lifting the counterweights partially out of their guide tubes. As a result, chain slack accumulated under the guards. The pressure of the bunched-up chains against

Figure 1.14: Fiber re-termination process – (a) We begin by cutting the ends of the first generation fiber jackets, being careful not to come in contact with the fiber core inside. (b) Using a stripping tool, we strip the fiber coating, such that it fits snugly inside a 330 μm ferrule. We seal the FC connector and ferrule tip (white), letting the epoxy settle for 24 hr (not depicted). (c) We use the ruby fiber scribe to very gently score the fiber above the epoxy bead, and (d) polish the fiber by working our way through polishing films of decreasing coarseness (30 μm – 1 μm). Throughout this step, we used a fiber scope (not depicted) to inspect the re-terminated fiber. Images (b)-(c) are taken from the THORLABS ‘Guide to Connectorization and Polishing Optical Fibers’ FN96A manual, which explains why the depicted fiber jacket is made up of (yellow) PVC. Our fiber jackets are made of steel, as Panel (a) shows.

the guards caused them to shatter. Consequently, the counter weights and their safety caps came out of their guides. In one of the Aqawans, as the counter weights tried to cross the sprocket, they overloaded the motor and triggered the emergency stop. In the other Aqawan, one of the U-joints broke as a result of the pressure, which stopped its respective motor. Figures 1.16 and 1.17 show some of the damage.

Figure 1.15: Old fiber throughput improvement following re-termination – Plot of normalized flux (counts per pixel) as a function of pixel number. The flux is normalized such that the counts per pixel, prior to re-termination, were equal to one (bottom). After re-termination, there is about a factor of ten improvement in light throughput (top). Telescope 1 (T1) is shown in *red*, T2 in *green*, T3 in *blue*, and T4 in *yellow*. Adviser Jason Eastman made this plot.

With the assistance of FLWO personnel, we were able to close the Aqawans shortly after the critical failure. We traveled to MINERVA in 2017 February in order to replace the broken U-joint. We also re-installed the limit-switches to prevent the counterweights from leaving their guiders. Figures 1.17, 1.18, and 1.19 depict the repair process. Lastly, we drew snow lines outside the Aqawans, which will act as snow depth gauges. The MINERVA control software already detects snow, and requires manual approval before it will open. Therefore, the snow line will also allow the observer to determine whether or not to open the Aqawans. Our repairs not only fix the hardware damage incurred, but also offer robust preventive measures against it happening again.

Unexpected delays due to the fiber installation and re-termination, and the Aqawan

failure, ultimately prevented me from using MINERVA to obtain new 55 Cnc RV measurements. However, the abundance of publicly-available data on the system (§3.3.1), as well as the 2017 Keck data release (Butler et al., 2017), allowed me to carry out the rest of my thesis goals without problems. Through this diverse set of hardware projects, I gained a much deeper understanding of the means through which instrumentalists use photons – collected in the telescope primary – to generate raw stellar spectra. With a re-terminated set of fibers, repaired Aqawan enclosures, and an improved snow-protection plan, MINERVA is closer than ever to begin its three-year RV survey (from a hardware point of view).

Figure 1.16: The three panels above show the cause and aftermath of the Aqawan failure. (a) The snow line prevented the Aqawan trigger wheels from activating their respective limit switches. (b) Limit switch disengaged (left) and engaged (right). (c) Aftermath of the failure: a bunched-up chain, broken guard, and counter weight out of its guide tube.

Figure 1.17: U-Joint repair process (a) Broken U-Joint mounted to the left of the motor. (b) In order to replace the broken U-Joint, we dismantled the pole and sprocket assembly, and (c) subsequently re-installed it, along with the new U-joint. (d) Newly-installed U-Joint (dark silver).

1.4 Modeling Stellar Spectra with MINERVA

1.4.1 A Note on Finding the Best Fit

Whether it be modeling stellar spectra (§ 1.4.4) radial velocity curves (§ 2.2.1), or phenomena beyond the scope of this thesis (and even astronomy), scientists are often trying to find the best fit, or more specifically generate a model, M , from a set of model parameters that describe a data set, D . In order to achieve this goal we often use Bayesian analysis, which allows us to incorporate evidence into our understanding of the studied phenomenon in a coherent manner (Blitzstein & Hwang, 2015). *Conditioning* is the statistical equivalent to

Figure 1.18: Limit-switch installation – (a) To prevent the counterweight from leaving its guide, LCOGT developers installed a limit switch atop the safety caps inside their smaller Aqawans. This configuration allows for the counterweight to trigger the limit switch - and thereby stop the motor - before leaving its guide tube. (b) We recreated this mechanism in our Aqawans using OSISWITCH ZCMD21C12 limit switches. (c and d) We machined clearance holes and screwed the limit switches to our safety caps. Our Aqawans are up-scaled versions of the LCOGT design. In turn, our guiding tubes are long enough that the safety cap switch is triggered *after* the shutter touch the ground. I.e., this limit switch configuration would be useless for MINERVA. We came up with an alternative solution, depicted in Figure 1.19.

“incorporating evidence”.¹⁴ In Bayesian analysis, finding the best fit is equivalent to finding the model parameter set M that best describes a given data set D , i.e., the model parameter set that maximizes the posterior probability, $P(M|D)$. By Bayes’ theorem (Bayes &

¹⁴Due to its central importance as the way in which we update beliefs to reflect evidence, *and* a problem-solving strategy, my statistics professor at Harvard, Joseph Blitzstein, often says that “*Conditioning is the soul of statistics*”.

Figure 1.19: Stage 2 of the MINERVA snow protection plan – We came up with an alternative limit switch mechanism installed on the side of the counterweight guiding tube. This design guarantees that the limit switch be triggered either before the counterweight leaves the guider, *or* the shutter touches the snow line.

Price, 1763), the probability of M conditional on D is defined as

$$P(M|D) = \frac{P(D|M)P(M)}{P(D)} \quad (1.1)$$

where $P(D|M)$, or the probability of D given M , is called the likelihood \mathcal{L} , and $P(M)$ is the prior probability of M , or the probability of the model before updating based on our evidence (which in this case is our data D). $P(D)$, the probability of the data set, can be

treated as a constant whenever we are evaluating different parameters of the same model. Thus, throughout this thesis $P(M|D) \propto P(D|M)P(M)$, and finding the best fit reduces to maximizing \mathcal{L} . If we assume that our data has Gaussian uncertainties σ , then then \mathcal{L} is given by

$$\mathcal{L} = P(D|M) = (2\pi)^{(-n/2)} \left[\prod_{i=1}^n (\sigma_i^2 + s^2)^{-1/2} \right] \times \exp \left[- \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(D_i - M_i)^2}{2(\sigma_i^2 + s^2)} \right] \quad (1.2)$$

with the i^{th} subscript corresponding to each of the n data points, and s defined to be a scatter term. Assuming constant scatter, the likelihood simplifies to

$$\mathcal{L} \propto \exp[-\chi^2/2] \quad \text{where} \quad \chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{D_i - M_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \quad (1.3)$$

From Eq. (1.3) we notice that maximizing the likelihood is equivalent to minimizing χ^2 when the term before the exponent is constant. As shown in Gould (2003), Eq. (1.3) may be solved analytically for linear models. However, non-linear models, such as radial velocities and spectra, require a numerical minimization of the χ^2 metric in order to find the best-fit parameters. The numerical minimization algorithm used is dependent upon the specific parameter space being explored. Throughout this thesis, I will discuss two different chi-square minimization strategies used to restrict the region of parameter space being explored near the global minimum. In Section 1.4.4, I describe the tricks specific to fitting spectra, and in Section 2.2.1, I explain those specific to fitting exoplanet RVs. Having constrained parameter space, a handful of routines are generally used to find the local minimum. The two that I use in this thesis are the Nelder-Mead (also known as simplex, or amoeba) method (Nelder, 1965), and the Levenberg-Marquardt(LM) method (Levenberg, 1944; Marquardt, 1963). The amoeba method crawls downhill with no assumptions about the function being evaluated, and as such is considered a robust, yet slow algorithm for unconstrained non-linear optimization. The LM method uses function derivatives to minimize along the direction opposite to the gradient of the function, i.e., the direction of

steepest decline of the χ^2 metric. As such, the LM method converges much more rapidly than the amoeba method, but may fail when parameter space is not very smooth.

1.4.2 The History of Precision Doppler Spectroscopy

In the early 1890s, Hermann Carl Vogel and Edward C. Pickering became the first astronomers to demonstrate Christian Doppler’s 1842 theory that stars moving along our line of sight would exhibit a change in color (Doppler, 1843). By means of this color change — also known as a Doppler shift — Vogel and Pickering discovered the first spectroscopic binary stars Algol and Zeta Ursae Majoris, respectively (Vogel, 1889; Pickering, 1890). However, it was not until 1952 that Struve proposed precision radial velocity (PRV) as a means to discover, not new binary systems, but indeed new worlds. Two decades later, Griffin & Griffin (1973) identified a major source of error in RV techniques of the day;. They found that systematic errors could arise as a result of the different optical paths traversed by the reference and stellar beams (from the primary to the spectrograph). They suggested that telluric lines at rest with respect to the spectrograph could serve as calibration sources. Specifically, these telluric line wavelength fiducials could illuminate the optics at the same time and along the same path as the astronomical light, thus reducing systematic errors. Consequently, differential measurements of the stellar line shifts with respect to telluric lines could result in Doppler precision of 10 m s^{-1} . This general approach was further developed by several groups (e.g., Campbell & Walker, 1979).

Of particular interest is the pioneering work of Campbell et al. (1988), who placed an absorption cell filled with hydrogen fluoride (HF) in the path of the telescope beam, and performed simultaneous wavelength calibration with its sparse (non-blended) and evenly space absorption lines in the red optical band. They achieved $10 - 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ precision. In 1992, Marcy & Butler proposed gaseous iodine (I_2) as a more effective absorption medium that could provide sharp, stable wavelength fiducials in the $5000 - 6200 \text{ \AA}$ range, with at least two features per \AA . In contrast to HF, iodine is chemically stable, only slightly

corrosive, and nonlethal. Lastly, iodine has a stronger line absorption coefficient than HF, which means that a 10 cm long absorption cell heated to $50 \pm 0.1^\circ \text{C}$ (in lieu of HF’s requirement of a meter-long one at 100°C) suffices for PRV. Because I_2 lines blend with stellar lines, a robust algorithm is needed to model the composite spectrum (see Section 1.4.3). Marcy & Butler (1992) installed iodine cells on the Hamilton spectrograph at Lick Observatory, eventually achieving 3 m s^{-1} precision (Marcy et al., 1997), as well as HIRES on Keck I, which in 2004 achieved $1 - 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ precision, the highest ever obtained with simultaneous calibration.¹⁵ Precise Doppler spectroscopy using iodine cell calibrators has yielded a multitude of exciting results, including the discovery of the first multiple-planet system (Butler et al., 1999) and the first ρ_{\oplus} (Earth density) exoplanets (Howard et al., 2013; Pepe et al., 2013).

A second technique, which we refer to as the parallel calibration approach, has also proved effective for PRV. This technique consists of taking a spectrum of known wavelength solution (e.g., a thorium argon lamp) before and after the stellar spectrum. In 1995, Mayor & Queloz used the parallel calibration technique to detect a planetary companion around 51 Peg b. The spectrograph involved in the detection – ELODIE – bypassed temporal and spatial errors in calibration by using two parallel fibers transporting starlight and light from a thorium argon (ThAr) lamp, respectively (Baranne et al., 1996). ELODIE achieved a velocity precision of $\sim 13 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Its successor, CORALIE, achieved $2 - 7 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ precision (Queloz et al., 2000). Later on, HARPS-S (Mayor et al., 2003) and HARPS-N (Cosentino et al., 2012) were built with ultra-stabilized vacuum enclosures. With an RV precision of 1 m s^{-1} , HARPS-S and HARPS-N are the state-of-the-art instruments using the parallel calibration technique.

The discovery of terrestrial planets, and a true analog to Earth, depends on our ability to breach the 1 m s^{-1} barrier we have been stuck in for the last decade. Earth-sized planets produce RV signatures of $\sim 10 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, below the current precision floor. Pushing down

¹⁵This state-of-the-art precision was achieved following the Keck 2004 CCD upgrade, as (Butler et al., 2017) details.

RV precision to the cm s^{-1} level requires an interdisciplinary effort. First is the need for instrumentation capable of obtaining extremely precise RV measurements. Impending ground-based observation facilities with powerful spectrographs, such as EXPRES on the Discovery Channel Telescope (Jurgenson et al., 2016), HPF on the Hobby-Eberly Telescope (Mahadevan et al., 2012), NEID on the WIYN Telescope (Kitt Peak National Observatory) (Schwab et al., 2016), and G-CLEF on the Giant Magellan Telescope (Szentgyorgyi et al., 2014) will fulfill these precision demands in the future.

Achieving RV precision of 10 cm s^{-1} will also require new data reduction techniques to model stellar activity, such as faculae, spots and plage (For a thorough description, see e.g., Haywood et al. (2016)). Stellar magnetic activity and stellar jitter are still relatively poorly understood, and can mimic RV signals. This has been known since 1996, when the understanding that stellar magnetic cycles cause apparent periodic changes in radial velocity led Butler et al. (1996) to conclude that “ultimately the limit to velocity precision is set by the stars themselves”. Recently, Gaussian Process (GP) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) have begun to show promise as techniques to account for stellar jitter (Haywood et al., 2016). For example, Lopez-Morales et al. (2016) used GP to determine the planetary mass of Kepler 21b. PCA operates on every pixel of the simulated stellar spectra so as to model different velocity features, such as spots and planets, separately. Fischer et al. (2016) outlines the current state of precise Doppler spectroscopy, and describes in detail the challenges in achieving 10 cm s^{-1} precision.

1.4.3 Modeling the Observations

MINERVA uses the iodine cell technique to calibrate stellar spectra, which relies on a forward modeling scheme to extract precise RV measurements (Butler et al., 1996). The algorithm consists of forward modeling the stellar spectra using synthetic or empirically derived reference spectra to find best-fit model parameters specified in Table [refTab1d](#). An observation through the iodine cell, $F_{\text{obs}}(x)$, is modeled as the product of the Doppler-

shifted intrinsic stellar spectrum, $F_*(\lambda)$, and the transmission function from the iodine cell, $F_{I_2}(\lambda)$. The product is then convolved with the spectral point spread function of the telescope,¹⁶ denoted by $\mathcal{P}(x)$, to return the normalized 1-D spectrum, $F_{\text{obs}}(x)$. Hence,¹⁷

$$F_{\text{obs}}(x) = [F_{I_2}(\lambda(x)) \times F'_*(\lambda(x))] * \mathcal{P}(x) \quad (1.4)$$

Notice the $\lambda(x)$ dependence of the iodine transmission function and intrinsic stellar spectrum, which is defined as the wavelength solution for the 1-D spectrum at any given pixel position and spectral order, x . Further, the intrinsic stellar spectrum is Doppler shifted such that $F'_*(\lambda(x)) = F_*(\lambda \cdot (1 + z))$, where z corresponds to the Doppler shift described by two components: the stellar RV, v_* , and the barycentric velocity of the telescope with respect to the star, v_{BC} (Wang, 2016).

We will now discuss the origin of the stellar and iodine templates, as well as the functional form of the IP in the context of MINERVA. Ideally, the reference spectra would consist of the intrinsic spectra of the sources, whether it be the iodine cell or the star. Since this is not possible, the stellar reference spectra for MINERVA targets are empirically derived from iodine-free stellar observations taken with Keck. Eventually, we plan to obtain empirically derived spectra of our target stars using KiwiSpec (Gibson et al., 2012). The iodine reference spectrum, or iodine atlas, was obtained via a Fourier Transform Spectrometer (FTS) scan of KiwiSpec’s I₂ cell. The scan used was taken with the Bruker IFS 125HR FTS (at The Pacific Northwestern Laboratory), which has a resolution of 0.002 cm⁻¹. Modeling the instrumental profile is an ongoing challenge for MINERVA. Indeed, finding a customized function that describes the IP for a spectrograph as precise as KiwiSpec is not only extremely difficult, but also crucial to achieve RV precision below 3 m s⁻¹. Generally, an IP can take on many functional forms. A common and effective IP

¹⁶ Also known as spectral response function or instrumental profile (IP).

¹⁷The mathematical notation used in this section is based on Dr. Wang’s PhD thesis (Wang, 2016).

consists of a sum of gaussians of the form

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{gaus}} = \sum A_n \exp \left[\left(\frac{x - \mu_n}{\sigma_n} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1.5)$$

where x represents the pixel position (or spectral order), and A_n , μ_n , σ_n represent the amplitude, position and width of the n^{th} Gaussian component, respectively. Keck/HIRES, for example, uses an IP that contains 12 free parameters A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{12} , with A_0 , μ_n and σ_n (for $n = 0, 1, \dots, 12$) fixed to empirically-optimized constant values, which Valenti et al. (1995) obtained rather heroically. Another common functional form used to model the IP is the Gauss-Hermite (GH) function (Wang, 2016):

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{GH}} = \sum A_n u_n(x) = \sum A_n \left(\frac{2}{\pi w^2} \right)^{1/4} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n!2^2}} H_n \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}x}{w} \right) \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x}{w} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1.6)$$

which is the product of a sum of gaussians and Hermite polynomials H_n . GH functions are mathematically advantageous as they are non-degenerate (whereas gaussians are) and in principle they can uniquely constrain any shape. In practice, however, the sensitivity of GH polynomials to initial guesses makes it difficult for the least- χ^2 solver to converge to an optimized solution for the numerous parameters. Although GH IP generally do not outperform a sum of satellite gaussians (e.g., Vanderburg et al., 2013), Wang (2016) was able to demonstrate their superiority, and successfully used them to extract extremely precise RVs from HET/HRS data. With the purpose of improving MINERVA's instrumental profile, I worked toward incorporating a GH IP into MINERVA's Doppler pipeline. In the process, I acquired a deeper understanding of the code in charge of modeling raw spectra, finding its redshift, and obtaining the corresponding RV datum. After presenting an overview of the MINERVA pipeline, I dedicate Section 1.4.5 toward describing my progress and findings on this front.

1.4.4 The MINERVA Pipeline

MINERVA’s Doppler pipeline, `fourchunkjj.py` was written from the ground up by Prof. John Johnson, with modifications by Dr. Eastman and Dr. Sharon Wang. It is based on the California Planet Survey (CPS) Doppler code, which extracts precise RVs from iodine-calibrated spectra. Drs. Paul Butler and Geoffrey Marcy drafted the first version of the CPS code in 1991, and Prof. Johnson has modified it heavily since 2002. While no documentation of this code exists in published or unpublished form, Butler et al. (1996) first described its basic form. The CPS code is used extensively in the exoplanet literature, and has enabled important exoplanet discoveries (e.g., Johnson et al., 2006; Howard et al., 2009, 2011; Johnson et al., 2011). `fourchunkjj.py` is translated from IDL to Python, and makes heavy use of object-oriented programming. At present, the pipeline can achieve 1 m s^{-1} precision.

Within `fourchunkjj.py`, the `Spectrum` class is instantiated with the fits file of a given observed spectrum we wish to model. Figure 1.10 shows one such raw spectrum taken with KiwiSpec. The stellar template, synthetic IP, and Iodine template are class variables within `Spectrum`. `Spectrum` obtains or calculates two barycentric (BC) redshift corrections: one for the observation, and another one for the stellar template. Another class, `FourChunk`, fits the spectra, defined in `Spectrum`, one 2\AA chunk at a time. Specifically, `FourChunk` sets up the Iodine interpolation function (Eq. 1.4), and defines the parameters used to forward-model the stellar spectra (as described in Section 1.4.3). The working version of `fourchunkjj.py` uses a 7-parameter model (Table 1.1). A set of 28 parameters (7 per telescope) is passed to `FourChunk`, wherein the method `model` generates four models (one per telescope) of a 2\AA chunk of the spectra. The method `mpfit_model`, also inside `FourChunk`, flattens the output from `model` and returns the $1 \times n$ array `(obs - model) / err`, which we contextualize below.

In order to fit the spectra and sample the parameter posteriors, `FourChunk` relies on the `mpyfit.fit` module, and a fitting method: `mpfitter`. However, these are

not currently being used due to efficiency considerations. Inside `mpfitter` the module `mpyfit.fit` performs a Levenberg-Marquardt least-squares minimization (using the output of `mpfit_model` as the argument of the χ^2 sum) and obtains best-fit parameters for the four models describing the 2\AA chunk (1 per telescope). Figure 1.20 shows one such 2\AA chunk.

Figure 1.20: Observed day-time spectrum overlaid with the best-fit spectral model we derived using `mpfitter`. Telescope 1 (T1) is shown in *red*, T2 in *green*, T3 in *blue*, and T4 in *yellow*. This color scheme shall remain consistent throughout this thesis. The discrepancy between T1 and T3 is attributable to the separate wavelength solution fit per trace. The data points at the bottom of the plot represent the residuals.

A third class, `grind`, is instantiated using an observation file of a complete spectrum. `grind` will then create a `FourChunk` object for each 2\AA chunk of the observed spectrum, and consequently fit all the chunks until it obtains a complete model of the observed

spectrum. In order to save all of the fitting information, `grind` constructs a record array that allows field access using attributes. Lastly, `globgrind` fits all observation files in a data directory, and `globgrindall` fits all observation files in all the data directories. Figure 1.21 shows a diagram of the CPS code structure.

Figure 1.21: Diagram of CPS code structure – From left to right, the diagram depicts the hierarchy of functions that the MINERVA Doppler pipeline uses to fit spectra.

Table 1.1: 7-Parameter model for forward-modeling stellar spectra using MINERVA.

Parameter	Unit and Meaning
z	no unit, the stellar redshift
w_o	Å, wavelength of the middle pixel of a spectral chunk
dw/dx	Å/ pixel, wavelength dispersion scale for a spectral chunk
α	continuum normalization
β	continuum shape slope
$A_n, n = 1, 2$	no unit, broadening and skew applied to theoretical (Zemax) IP

1.4.5 Testing the 22-Parameter Model

In order to familiarize myself with MINERVA’s Doppler pipeline, I assessed the feasibility of incorporating Hermite-Gaussian polynomials into `FourChunk` to improve the IP-characterization of the array, which could ultimately increase its RV precision. To this end,

adviser Jason Eastman provided me with an incomplete version of the Doppler pipeline, with a partially incorporated 22-parameter (per telescope) spectral model. In contrast to the 7-parameter model, the 22-parameter model includes a spectrum curvature term, d^2w/dx^2 (the second derivative of wavelength with respect to pixel position), as well as 15 Hermite Polynomial coefficients (Table 1.2). The incomplete version of the code included an identical `Spectrum` class, and a partially-modified `FourChunk` class with a record array ready to accommodate 22 parameters.

Table 1.2: 22-Parameter model for forward-modeling stellar spectra using MINERVA

Parameter	Unit and Meaning
z	no unit, the stellar redshift
w_o	Å, wavelength of the middle pixel of a spectral chunk
dw/dx	Å/ pixel, wavelength dispersion scale for a spectral chunk
d^2w/dx^2	Å ² / pixel ² , wavelength curvature scale for a spectral chunk
α	continuum normalization
β	continuum shape slope
$H_n, n = 1, 2, \dots, 15$	no unit, values for Hermite polynomial coefficients

I began by rewriting the `model` function within `FourChunk` to incorporate the 88 parameters (22 parameters/telescope). Although the results from Wang (2016) provided some motivation to stick with this formidable parameter-space, I set out to generate covariance plots in order to discard highly-correlated parameters. Specifically, I modified the `model` function to generate a *single* 88-parameter model for the four telescopes, and wrote an `emcee_fitter` function which relies on the `mpyfit.fit` module and a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) ensemble sampler (Foreman-Mackey et al., 2013) to find best-fit parameter values, and sample the parameter posteriors.¹⁸ It is worth noting that the MCMC process is initialized with so-called “walkers” positioned throughout parameter space, with coordinates $p_{w,i}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n_{\text{walkers}}$), given (in this case) by the best-fit 22-parameter

¹⁸Seeing as covariance plots require the posterior distribution of each parameter, the implemented MCMC fitter also meant that `lnprior`, `lnlikelihood`, and `lnposterior` methods had to be implemented.

values, p_{BF} , plus a constant C :

$$\begin{aligned} p_{w,i} &= p_{\text{BF}} + C \\ &= p_{\text{BF}} + \left[\frac{1}{10} \times \text{jiggle_amp} \times p_{\text{BF}} \times n_{\text{Gaussian},i} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (1.7)$$

Here, `jiggle_amp` is given by a uniform deviate large enough to prevent discrete parameter space exploration, but small enough so as to not to dominate the steps taken by the walkers.¹⁹ Since there was no prior information regarding appropriate deviate values for the 88 parameters, our initial `jiggle_amp` array featured 88 uniform deviates of value 10^{-7} .²⁰

The modifications I made to the code have the added benefit of generating *a single* spectral best-fit model for the observed target (with uncertainties), thereby resulting in a single best-fit redshift value that is ultimately converted into a RV datum (§2.1.1). I used the modified LM + MCMC routine to fit a 2\AA chunk,²¹ hoping that a $\sim 40,000$ step chain would yield a best-fit model, as well as covariance plots. *For reasons I explain below, such was not the case.*

The sensitivity of the least- χ^2 solver to initial guesses made it challenging for the chains to converge to an optimized solution for the 88 parameters. While the choice of a uniform deviate was necessary in order to initialize the MCMC process, the dynamic ranges of the 88 parameters deviate by orders of magnitude. Therefore, it became apparent that the `jiggle_amp` values had to be tuned independently.²² Our tuning strategy was the following:

¹⁹The series of steps generated by each walker is usually called a chain.

²⁰ This choice, while problematic, was unavoidable at this stage. I attempted a plethora of values which were at times too small to allow the chains to spread, and at times large enough to step out of parameter space (thereby crashing the code). After three weeks of debugging, I finally found that a uniform deviate of $1\text{e-}7$ could get us started

²¹I purposefully chose the same chunk that is fitted in Fig. 1.20.

²²I adopted the same deviate for analogous parameters, since they are expected to have near-identical values. E.g., I adopt the same redshift deviate for the redshift parameter corresponding to telescopes one through four.

1. Beginning with a uniform deviate of 10^{-7} for all parameters, carry out an MCMC chain with 200 walkers (i.e, 200 chains). Allow the MCMC chain to run for $\sim 42,000$ steps (= 12 hr), with a “burn-in” stage of 8000 steps ($\sim 20\%$ of the total).
2. Plot each parameter chain separately, and find the maximum and minimum parameter values. For each parameter, inspect the chain, *assessing qualitatively* whether it seems well-mixed, or whether the deviate must be increased/decreased. See Fig. 1.22b for a description of this qualitative assessment (QA).
3. Redefine `jiggle_amp` individually for each parameter, using (max. param. value – min. param. value) as a guideline for the order of magnitude of the deviate.
4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 as many times as possible.²³

1.4.5.1 Discussion

I begin by re-stating that this was an exploratory exercise, where the difference between chains that look qualitatively well-mixed, and those that do not, is obvious. The results of the fine-tuning are summarized in Figure 1.22, where I show three parameters (α , ω_0 , and hp_1) representative of the variety of chains obtained for all the parameters. The left column of Figure 1.22 demonstrates how a 42000-step MCMC process evolved prior to applying the fine-tuning algorithm. The right column provides examples of qualitatively well-mixed (α), and non well-mixed chains (ω_0 , and hp_1). Most importantly, *from looking at Fig. 1.22, it is evident that the 22-parameter model did not converge to a solution*. As a result, I was unable to generate covariance plots to assess the correlation between the 88 parameters in the model. Nonetheless, the progress made in fine-tuning the `jiggle_amp` values of some of the parameters reveals that I was heading in the right direction. This fine-tuning strategy exhibited uneven success across the 22 parameters, when comparing their convergence level qualitatively, and relative to each other. Specifically, the chains of

²³As I discuss in the next section, this tuning is not efficient, but it is effective. The limiting factor in iterating through steps 2-3 was time.

parameters α and β (Fig. 1.22b) appear to be better well-mixed than those of w_0 , dw/dx , d^2w/dx^2 and σ (Fig. 1.22d). The chains for all the GH coefficients, and z exhibit the worse state of convergence (Fig. 1.22f).

Unsurprisingly, this heuristic method for fine-tuning deviates failed in the case of GH coefficients (Fig 1.22f). This could be happening due to a number of reasons. It might be the case that the `mpyfit.fit` routine is not robust enough to pin down the best-fit value for the coefficients, thereby resulting in a starting position which is very far away from the global minimum. Despite increasing the `jiggle_` for all GH coefficients by over three orders of magnitude over the span of this exercise, it could still be the case that the step size is still too small, thereby resulting in highly correlated chains which explore parameter space, but only discretely. Lastly, this could be an indication that indeed we are dealing with several highly correlated parameters. More robust fine-tuning of all the GH deviates is required before determining which of the above options is the culprit of the behavior exhibited by these chains.

If it is the case that improving the IP of MINERVA will allow it to achieve RV precision of $\lesssim 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, it might be worth automating this fine-tuning process. In lieu of iterating through steps (1)-(4), such an automation would require (more reliable) quantitative methods to assess the convergence of an MCMC chain. One such quantitative method is the Gelman-Rubin statistic, \hat{R}_z . \hat{R}_z quantifies whether a set of chains are well-mixed by comparing the variance within a random chain (for one parameter) to the variance between the chains (for that same parameter). Once the chains “have forgotten” their initial value, they are considered to be well-mixed (Gelman & Rubin, 1992). Incidentally, we now have the experience necessary to easily alter the current 7-parameter Doppler pipeline so that it generates a *single* 28-parameter spectral model. For these reasons, our study represents an important, yet qualitative, stepping stone toward the improvement of the MINERVA IP.

(a) Parameter α with deviate of 10^{-7} – While most chains remain concentrated near $\alpha \approx 9.9 \times 10^4$, and some errant chains evolve near $\alpha \approx 9.2 \times 10^4$ and 1.05×10^5 . The initial guess of 10^{-7} is too small for parameter α .

(b) Parameter α with deviate of 4.01×10^2 – All the chains centered around $\alpha \approx 9.8 \times 10^4$, consistent with the region of greatest concentration in Fig. 1.22a. Comparatively, the chains for parameter α appear closest to convergence.

(c) Parameter ω_0 with deviate of 10^{-7} – A single errant chain is present near 5288.49. The initial guess of 10^{-7} is too small for parameter ω_0 .

(d) Parameter ω_0 with deviate of 5.2×10^{-6} – Greatest concentration of chains consistent with Fig. 1.22c. Some errant chains persist. ω_0 is further from convergence than α .

(e) Parameter hp_1 (the first-order GH polynomial) with deviate of 10^{-7} – The flaring of this chain indicates highly-covariant steps, and/or a poorly-constrained initial guess.

(f) Parameter hp_1 with deviate of 27.9 – The flaring is persistent. In comparison to the above cases, the GH polynomials and z appear to be furthest from convergence.

Figure 1.22: Overview of the fine-tuning exercise for select parameters – The left column shows the evolution of a 42000-step MCMC run running 200 parallel chains, and using a uniform deviate of 10^{-7} for all parameters. The right column represents the evolution of a 42000-step MCMC run running 200 parallel chains, and using independently fine-tuned deviates for each parameter.

Chapter 2

SINGLE-PLANET SYSTEMS

2.1 Fitting One Planet

Chapter 1 explained how MINERVA's RV pipeline forward models the observed spectrum in order to obtain the redshift, z , of an observed star. This chapter is dedicated to presenting a thorough review of the conversion from z to an RV datum. Here, I also describe EXOFAST (Eastman et al., 2013), an IDL software package which MINERVA will use in order to fit RV and transit curves of its target stars. The chapter begins with a thorough overview of the one-planet fitting process. I review the consequences of the gravitational interaction between a star and a planet in Section 2.1.1, and arrive at the RV model used by EXOFAST to obtain RV curves for single-planet systems. Section 2.2 describes the specific procedure that EXOFAST uses to fit RV data, including its unique parametrization. Finally, I discuss the shortcomings of EXOFAST in the context of fitting multiple planet systems, paving the way to introduce a new version of the code in Chapter 3.

2.1.1 The Two-Body Problem¹

The two-body problem describes two bodies exerting mutual gravitational attraction on each other as they orbit their common center of mass, which provides a suitable context to understand the motion of a planet around a star. Between 1609 and 1619, Kepler used an empirical approach to derive his three laws of planetary motion, which included the observation that planets move in ellipses around the Sun. Later, in 1687, Newton demonstrated that this elliptical motion stemmed from the inverse square law of force acting between a planet and the Sun – namely, the universal law of gravitation – given by

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2} \quad (2.1)$$

If we take m_1 and m_2 to be the mass of the star and the planet, respectively, with two-dimensional position vectors \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 originating from the inertial center of mass O of the two-body system, the relative motion of the planet with respect to the star is described by the vector $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1$ (Fig. 2.3). Consequently, the gravitational force acting on the star due to the presence of the planet, and viceversa, is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = m_1 \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_1 = +G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^3} \mathbf{r} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{F}_2 = m_2 \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_2 = -G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^3} \mathbf{r} \quad (2.2)$$

Furthermore, taking the second derivative of $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1$ yields

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}} = \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_2 - \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_1 \quad (2.3)$$

If we solve Eqs.(2.2) for $\ddot{\mathbf{r}}_1$ and $\ddot{\mathbf{r}}_2$, and plug these into Eq.(2.3), we obtain the second order

¹The derivation of the two-body problem presented in this section follows the reasoning of Murray & Dermott (2000) and Seager et al. (2010) (Ch.2 & Ch.3), and is meant to demonstrate my understanding of the RV equation.

differential equation of relative motion, which describes the path of m_2 with respect to m_1 :

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}} + G(m_1 + m_2)\frac{\hat{\mathbf{r}}}{r^2} = 0 \quad (2.4)$$

In order to solve Eq.(2.4), we switch coordinate systems from Cartesian to polar, $(x, y) \Rightarrow (r, \theta)$. Letting $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ represent unit vectors parallel and perpendicular to the radial direction, we may write the position, velocity, and acceleration vectors as

$$\mathbf{r} = r\hat{\mathbf{r}} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\mathbf{r}} = \dot{r}\hat{\mathbf{r}} + r\dot{\theta}\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \quad \text{and} \quad \ddot{\mathbf{r}} = (\ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2)\hat{\mathbf{r}} + \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dt} (r^2\dot{\theta}) \right] \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \quad (2.5)$$

Comparing the $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ components of Eq.(2.4) and the expression for $\ddot{\mathbf{r}}$ in Eq.(2.5), we obtain a scalar equation for the relative motion which equates two of Newton's famous laws: the second law ($F = m\mathbf{a}$) and the law of universal gravitation, Eq.(2.1)

$$\ddot{r} - r\dot{\theta}^2 = -G\frac{m_1 + m_2}{r^2} \quad (2.6)$$

In order to eliminate time from the above equation and solve for $r(\theta)$, we employ the substitutions $u = 1/r$, and $h = r^2\dot{\theta}$ (where h corresponds to the magnitude of the angular momentum), and find the first and second derivatives of u with respect to θ

$$\frac{du}{d\theta} = \frac{d}{d\theta} \frac{1}{r} = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{1}{r} \frac{dt}{d\theta} = -\frac{\dot{r}}{r^2\dot{\theta}} = -\frac{\dot{r}}{h} \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} = \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(-\frac{\dot{r}}{h} \right) = -\frac{1}{h} \frac{d\dot{r}}{dt} \frac{dt}{d\theta} = -\frac{\ddot{r}r^2}{h^2} \quad (2.8)$$

We may now use Eqs.(2.7) and (2.8) to express Eq.(2.6) in terms of u and θ

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\theta^2} + u = G\frac{m_1 + m_2}{h^2} \quad (2.9)$$

which is known as Binet's equation, and has general solution (in terms of u and r , respec-

tively):²

$$u(\theta) = p(1 + e \cos(\theta - \bar{\omega})) \Rightarrow r(\theta) = \frac{p}{1 + e \cos(\theta - \bar{\omega})} \quad (2.10)$$

where $p = \frac{h^2}{G(m_1+m_2)}$. Note that Eq.(2.10) is the general equation of a conic section in polar coordinates, where e and $\bar{\omega}$ are two constants of integration interpreted as the *eccentricity* and *phase* of the conic section, respectively, and p is the *semialtus rectum*. Kepler’s first law of planetary motion – that the planets move in ellipses with the Sun at one focus – informs our choice of e and p in equation (2.10), namely

$$0 \leq e < 1 \quad \text{and} \quad p = a(1 - e^2) \quad (2.11)$$

where a is the semimajor axis of the ellipse (Fig. 2.1a). Let us now interpret θ and $\bar{\omega}$ physically. The angle θ is called the *true longitude*, and measures the angular position of the planet along its orbit with respect to a reference line fixed in inertial space, which we conveniently choose to be our line-of-sight (or reference) direction. Recall that the vector $\mathbf{r} = r\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ measures the distance between the star and the planet. Consequently, invoking Eq.(2.10), the maximum and minimum separation between the two bodies occurs when

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\max} = \bar{\omega} + \pi &\rightarrow r = \frac{a(1 - e)(1 + e)}{1 + e \cos \pi} = a(1 + e) \rightarrow \text{“apastron”} \\ \theta_{\min} = \bar{\omega} &\rightarrow r = \frac{a(1 - e)(1 + e)}{1 + e \cos 0} = a(1 - e) \rightarrow \text{“periastron”} \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Thus it is no surprise that $\bar{\omega}$ is referred to as the longitude of periastron, and gives the angular location of closest approach with respect to the reference direction. In general, however, it is more convenient to refer the angular coordinate to the location of the perias-

²The reader may be wondering whether r can be expressed as a function of t . The answer is yes - this is the Kepler problem. While I won’t go into detail regarding the solution to the Kepler problem, the curious reader may refer to Murray & Dermott (2000) for details.

tron,³ which leads to the introduction of the angle $f = \theta - \bar{\omega}$; the *true anomaly*.⁴ In terms of f , the position and velocity of the planet become

$$r = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos f} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{r} = \frac{r f e \sin f}{1 + e \cos f} \quad (2.13)$$

All of the above physical variables are defined in Figure 2.1a.

2.1.1.1 The Orbit in Three Dimensions

Although in the above discussion I demonstrated that orbital motion is confined to a fixed orbital plane defined by three constants (e , a , and $\bar{\omega}$) motion in the Universe is not confined to a single plane. Therefore, it becomes pertinent to consider a three-dimensional orbital Cartesian coordinate system (Fig. 2.2) where a planet's position vector is given by

$$\mathbf{r} = x\hat{\mathbf{x}} + y\hat{\mathbf{y}} + z\hat{\mathbf{z}} \quad (2.14)$$

Just like in Figure 2.1b, the orbital plane lies along the xy-plane; the x-axis lies along the major axis of the ellipse and is co-linear with the periastron of the ellipse, the y-axis is perpendicular to the x-axis, and the z-axis is mutually perpendicular to the x and y axes such that the three are oriented according to the right-handed rule. We will now refer the orbital plane to a standard reference plane defined by the right-handed coordinate system (X,Y,Z), with the X-axis pointing toward the reference direction and the Z-axis pointing in the direction of the observer's line of sight. Furthermore, we let i denote the *inclination angle*, i.e., the angle between the orbital plane and the reference plane (XY-plane). The line formed by the intersection between the aforementioned planes is called the *line of nodes*, with the *ascending node* representing the location where the orbit crosses the reference plane

³except when $e = 0$, because then the periastron is no longer defined and one must choose a random direction. Throughout this thesis, we follow the convention that $\omega_* = \pi/2$ when the orbit is circular. As we will see in Section. 2.2.1.3, this implies that the time of transit occurs at periastron.

⁴For future reference, note that $\dot{f} = \dot{\theta}$.

(a) Depiction of the forces acting on a star of mass m_1 , and a planet of mass m_2 Illustration taken from Seager et al. (2010).

(b) Geometry of an ellipse, with relevant parameters clearly labeled. Illustration from Seager et al. (2010).

Figure 2.1: Visualizing the two-body problem.

from below. Consequently, Ω refers to the angle between the reference direction (X-axis) and the radial vector pointing toward the ascending node. Lastly, the angle between the radial vector and the orbital periastron, ω_* , added to Ω forms the non-coplanar, or “dog-leg” (Murray & Dermott, 2000), angle $\bar{\omega} = \Omega + \omega_*$.

Transforming any location in the orbital plane (x, y, z) to the standard reference plane (X, Y, Z) may be carried out by a series of three rotations: (i) a rotation of ω degrees about the z axis such that the x-axis is colinear with the line of nodes, (ii) a rotation about the

x axis of i degrees such that the orbital plane coincides with the XY-plane, and lastly (iii) a rotation about the z axis of Ω degrees. Representing the above transformations using standard 3×3 matrices $\mathbf{P}_j(\phi)$, where j is the axis of rotation and ϕ is the angle of rotation, we may describe the column vector (X, Y, Z) in terms of coordinates in the orbital plane:

$$\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix} = r \begin{pmatrix} \cos \Omega \cos(\omega + f) - \sin \Omega \sin(\omega + f) \cos i \\ \sin \Omega \cos(\omega + f) + \cos \Omega \sin(\omega + f) \cos i \\ \sin(\omega + f) \sin i \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.15)$$

We will return to Eq.(2.15) after determining the observable effects of an orbiting planet on its parent star, as seen from the barycenter, or center of mass of the system (Fig 2.3).

2.1.1.2 Barycentric Orbits

We have already solved for the motion of m_2 with respect to m_1 under suitable starting conditions (Eq.(2.10)), and defined a three-dimensional standard reference frame in which to place any orbit in space. Let us now revisit the two-body problem, this time using O' , the barycenter, as the origin of our coordinate system (Fig. 2.3). Referring to Figure 2.3, the position vector of the center of mass of the system is

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (2.16)$$

We may rewrite the above equation as

$$m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2 - (m_1 + m_2) \mathbf{R} = 0 \quad (2.17)$$

The above sum of the coefficients in Eq.(2.17) must be zero, such that we may conclude that the points defined by the three positions \mathbf{R} , \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 are co-linear. Furthermore,

Figure 2.2: Visualization of a 3D orbit, with all relevant parameters clearly labeled. Illustration from Seager et al. (2010).

Figure 2.3: Redefined position vectors of the star and planet with respect to the origin, O , and the center for mass of the system, O' . Illustration from Seager et al. (2010).

referring back to Fig. 2.3 we may write

$$\mathbf{R}_1 = \mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{R} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{R}_2 = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{R} \quad (2.18)$$

Plugging these back into Eq.(2.17) we get that

$$m_1 \mathbf{R}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{R}_2 = 0 \quad (2.19)$$

The above equation implies that (i) \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 are opposite and co-linear, (ii) their sum defines the separation between the two masses, namely $R_1 + R_2 = r$, and (iii) the *distances* of the masses with respect to the barycenter are related by $m_1 R_1 = m_2 R_2$. From (ii) and (iii) we obtain a system of two equations and solve for the two unknowns R_1 and R_2 to get that

$$R_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} r \quad \text{and} \quad R_2 = \frac{m_1}{m_1 + m_2} r \quad (2.20)$$

which implies that each mass in the two-body system will orbit the center of mass of the system in a path described by the conic section, Eq.(2.10), but with the semimajor axes reduced by a scale factor

$$a_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} a \quad \text{and} \quad a_2 = \frac{m_1}{m_1 + m_2} a \quad (2.21)$$

Equations (2.20) and (2.21) allow us to describe, for example, the equation of the ellipse of the first body around the barycenter. Using Eq.(2.13), we may write

$$r_1 = \frac{a_1(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos f} = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \cdot \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cos f} \quad (2.22)$$

Let us also obtain the first derivative of r_1 with respect to f , which will come in handy in

the next section:

$$\dot{r}_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \left[\frac{-a(1 - e^2)(-\dot{f}e \sin f)}{(1 + e \cos f)^2} \right] = \frac{r_1^2 e \dot{f} \sin f}{a_1(1 - e^2)} \quad (2.23)$$

2.1.1.3 Radial Velocity Signature of Keplerian Motion

We now have the tools to derive the relation between the position of a body in its orbit, and its radial velocity. Note that our observable will be the radial velocity of the star, which has mass m_1 . We begin by describing the relation between the position of m_1 in terms of f (Eq. (2.13)), and its orbital velocity, which we will have to project onto the object-to-observer line of sight (the Z-axis in Fig. 2.2). Recalling the Cartesian coordinate system described in Fig. 2.1b, we may write the position and velocity vectors for the star as

$$\mathbf{r}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cos f \\ r_2 \cos f \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.24)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{r}_1 \cos f - r_1 \dot{f} \sin f \\ \dot{r}_1 \sin f + r_1 \dot{f} \cos f \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.25)$$

We now wish to express \dot{r}_1 and \dot{f} as functions of f , such that we may describe the velocity as a single-variable function. Plugging in Eq.(2.23) into Eq.(2.25), and using the angular momentum relation $h_1 = m_1 r_1^2 \dot{f}$, we may express $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$ as

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{h_1}{m_1 a_1 (1 - e^2)} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin f \\ \cos f + e \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.26)$$

We then invoke proportion Eq.(2.20) and $h = r^2 \dot{\theta}$ to rewrite

$$h_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} h = \sqrt{\frac{G m_1^2 m_2^4 a (1 - e^2)}{(m_1 + m_2)^3}} \quad (2.27)$$

Substitute h_1 in Eq.(2.26), and write $\dot{\mathbf{r}}(f)$

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = \sqrt{\frac{Gm_2^2}{m_1 + m_2} \frac{1}{a(1 - e^2)}} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin f \\ \cos f + e \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.28)$$

Our last step consists of projecting the above equation onto the $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}$ direction in order to obtain the radial velocity equation

$$\begin{aligned} RV(t) &= \dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{Gm_2^2}{m_1 + m_2} \frac{1}{a(1 - e^2)}} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin f \\ \cos f + e \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sin \omega \sin i \\ \cos \omega \sin i \\ \cos i \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{Gm_2^2}{m_1 + m_2} \frac{1}{a(1 - e^2)}} [(-\sin f \sin \omega \sin i) + (\cos f + e)(\cos \omega \sin i) + \cancel{0(\cos i)}] \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{Gm_2^2}{m_1 + m_2} \frac{1}{a(1 - e^2)}} \sin i [-\sin f \sin \omega + \cos f \cos \omega + e \cos \omega] \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{Gm_2^2}{m_1 + m_2} \frac{1}{a(1 - e^2)}} \sin i [\cos(f + \omega) + e \cos \omega] \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

2.1.1.4 Doppler Effect

The above derivation led us to Eq.(2.29), where we effectively model our observable – the radial velocity of the star – in terms of the parameters of the system. The question then becomes, how do we measure our observable? By making use of the well-known Doppler effect. In flat spacetime (special relativity) an observer moving with respect to a source, emitted at wavelength λ_o , will measure a wavelength λ given by Einstein (1905):

$$\lambda = \lambda_o \frac{1 + \frac{1}{c} \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (2.30)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$ is the velocity of the source with respect to the observer (the target star in our context), and $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}$ is the unit vector pointing from the observer to the source in the inertial frame of the observer. Nonetheless, in the framework of general relativity, the curvature of spacetime results in a *gravitational redshift* that alters Eq.(2.30). For an observer at zero gravitational potential⁵

$$\lambda = \lambda_o \frac{1 + \frac{1}{c} \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}}{1 - \frac{\Phi}{c^2} - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (2.31)$$

where Φ is the Newtonian gravitational potential at the source. The fact that the Doppler shift equation relates frequency of light⁶ with velocity of the emitting source allows us to measure stellar radial velocity as a function of time. In practice, we obtain the Doppler shift from a number of spectral lines in the stellar spectra *after* correcting for the Earth's rotation and revolution around the Sun. Consequently, a suitable reference system centered at the barycenter of the Solar System, known as the International Celestial Reference System (ICRS), is used to transform measured wavelengths at Earth to barycentric wavelengths:

$$\lambda_B = \lambda_{\text{obs}} \frac{1 + \frac{1}{c} \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{\text{obs}}}{1 - \frac{\Phi_{\text{obs}}}{c^2} - \frac{v_{\text{obs}}^2}{c^2}} \quad (2.32)$$

The above barycentric correction equation describes the wavelength measured in the ICRS frame, λ_B as a function of the wavelength measured in the Earth frame λ_{obs} , the velocity of the observer with respect to the ICRS frame, $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_{\text{obs}}$, and the gravitational potential at the observer, Φ_{obs} . The relativistic terms in the denominator exhibit variations at the level of only 0.1 m s^{-1} over a year due to Earth's eccentric orbit. Therefore, when aiming for RV precision $> 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, these terms can be neglected such that Eq.(2.32) reduces to the Doppler shift formula in the classical regime, namely

$$\lambda_B = \lambda_{\text{obs}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{c} \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{\text{obs}} \right) \quad (2.33)$$

⁵See Lindegren & Dravins (2003) for a complete derivation.

⁶Although the formulas presented here are in terms of wavelength, one can convert them to frequency, ν , via $c = \lambda\nu$.

Having corrected the Earth-bound wavelength scale to the barycentric scale, we may finally obtain the radial velocity of the source from Eq.(2.31), again neglecting the relativistic terms in the denominators to obtain

$$\lambda_B = \lambda_o \left(1 + \frac{1}{c} \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} \right) \Rightarrow \hat{\mathbf{Z}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} = c \frac{\lambda_B - \lambda_o}{\lambda_o} = cz \quad (2.34)$$

Combining equations (2.29) and (2.34), we obtain the exact formula through which we may quantify the radial velocity in terms of our observable, namely the value of z that we obtain from the spectral fit.

2.2 EXOFAST

Section 2.1 delved into a detailed derivation of the radial velocity equation (2.29), that is generally used to model a one-planet system. This derivation used the solution strategies from Murray & Dermott (2000) & Seager et al. (2010). I now describe the software package that MINERVA will use in order to produce radial velocity curves of planetary systems, namely EXOFAST (Eastman et al., 2013). As will become evident, EXOFAST has ample applications beyond RV characterization of MINERVA targets. As of 2013, there existed several public codes capable of modeling transit light curves and/or radial velocities (e.g., Gazak et al., 2012; Southworth, 2008; Prša & Zwitter, 2005). However, unlike EXOFAST, none of them provided simultaneous and self-consistent fitting of radial velocities, transits, and stellar parameters, *as well as* a robust Differential Evolution Markov Chain (DE-MC) characterization of uncertainties. EXOFAST was thus written to provide a modular, non-interactive framework capable not only of fitting transit and RV data for single-planet systems, but also becoming adapted to analyze additional effects (e.g., secondary eclipses), and implementing different priors for the model parameters. All the EXOFAST documentation is available as an online applet.⁷ I used an online tutorial fitting of HAT-P-3b to

⁷<http://astroutils.astronomy.ohio-state.edu/exofast/>

familiarize myself with the software.

2.2.1 Methodology

2.2.1.1 Best Fit & Uncertainties

EXOFAST takes a Bayesian approach to determining the best-fit parameters of a single-planet system (§1.4.1), and uses the amoeba (simplex) method to find the local minimum. Prior to finding the local minimum, EXOFAST restricts the region of parameter space close to the global minimum by means of a parametrization scheme specific to exoplanets, which Eastman et al. (2013) describe in detail. The software uses the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) technique to sample the posteriors of the derived parameters, and report 1σ uncertainties. Eastman et al. (2013) also adopt the Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm as the means to determine how to step through $P(M|D)$. A step is accepted when the ratio of the likelihood between subsequent steps is larger than a random number drawn from a uniform distribution. As the MH algorithm guides the MCMC process, the code steps through parameter space, effectively sampling the probability density function (PDF) of each parameter. From this sample, EXOFAST reports a mean and 1σ error bars.

EXOFAST adopts the Differential-Evolution Markov Chain method (DE-MC) to determine an appropriate stepping scale with which to explore parameter space. This method was first described by ter Braak (2006), who showed that the difference between two random chains in an ensemble of many could provide an estimate for an ideal step size. The DE-MC algorithm uses such an estimate to converge towards a solution much more efficiently. The DE-MC algorithm also requires that a random, uniform deviate be added to each step in order to prevent discreet exploration of parameter space, which complicates its implementation in the context of exoplanets, because the best-fit parameters of an RV fit may differ by orders of magnitude. In the case of a multi-planetary fit, for example, a short-period planet may have uncertainties in the order of 10^{-4} days, whereas a long period planet may have an uncertainty of 10^2 . EXOFAST automatically estimates an ideal

random deviate for each parameter with the program EXOFAST_GETMCMCSCALE.

The MCMC process is thus initialized with each parameter in each of the chains at the best-fit value (obtained via the simplex method) plus a constant C , which is given by

$$C = 5 \times \text{EXOFAST_GETMCMCSCALE deviate} \times n_G \quad (2.35)$$

where n_G is a Gaussian-distributed random number. EXOFAST uses the guidelines established in Ford (2006) to determine when the MCMC chains have converged to the best-fit value. Specifically, they calculate the number of draws, T_z , and the Gelman-Rubin statistic, \hat{R}_z . The chains of any given fit are considered to be well-mixed when $T_z > 1000$ and a $\hat{R}_z < 1.01$ for six consecutive tests of increasing step number. In order to eliminate bias due to the starting conditions of the fit, EXOFAST finds the first point at which all the chains have a χ^2 below the median χ^2 , and consequently discard every step taken before that point. This is generally referred to as the “burn-in” stage. To diminish the memory allocation requirements of a fit, EXOFAST is capable of thinning the chains by a factor of N_{THIN} , inputted by the user, such that only every N_{THIN} link is stored. Once the fit has concluded, EXOFAST will output the histogram of steps for each parameter, which is proportional to the underlying posterior probability distribution, and quote the median of the distribution as the final value, along with a 1σ uncertainty.

2.2.1.2 RV Modeling

EXOFAST requires a model M in order to describe the gravitational interaction between a planet and its host star. Such an interaction is described by the radial velocity equation, Eq.(2.29), which I derived from first principles in Section 2.1.1. Defining $m_1 = M_*$, $m_2 = M_P$, the true anomaly as a function of time, $f = \theta(t)$, and recalling Kepler’s third law of planetary motion, Eq.(2.29) becomes:

$$RV(t) = K[\cos(\theta(t) + \omega_*) + e \cos \omega_*] + \gamma + \dot{\gamma}(t - t_0) \quad (2.36)$$

where K is the radial velocity semi-amplitude given by⁸

$$K = \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P(M_* + M_p)^2} \right)^{1/3} \frac{M_p \sin i}{\sqrt{1 - e^2}} \quad (2.37)$$

In addition to invoking Kepler’s third law to rewrite Eq.(2.29), Eastman et al. (2013) have also added two terms: γ , which is formally known as the systemic velocity and often represents an instrumental offset; and $\dot{\gamma}(t - t_0)$ – correspondingly, the systemic acceleration – which is generally used to account for additional trends, or periodicities in the data. As mentioned in Section 2.1.1, the solution to the Kepler problem allows us to solve for the position of the planet in its orbit as a function of time, $r(t)$. In turn, the solution to the Kepler problem tells us that $\theta(t)$ is given by⁹

$$\theta(t) = 2 \arctan \left[\sqrt{\frac{1 + e}{1 - e}} \tan \left(\frac{E(t)}{2} \right) \right] \quad (2.38)$$

In the context of the Kepler problem derivation, a new variable $E(t)$ – the eccentric anomaly – is defined in order to find an expression for r in terms of \dot{r} . $E(t)$ is given by the transcendental equation

$$M(t) = E(t) - e \sin E(t) \quad (2.39)$$

where $M(t)$ is the mean anomaly. EXOFAST solves the above equation numerically using EXOFAST_KEPLEREQ. Furthermore, defining T_P as the time of periastron passage

$$M(t) = \frac{2\pi}{P}(t - T_P) \quad (2.40)$$

Equations (2.38), (2.39) and (2.40) allow us to calculate the time t at which the planet will be at a given true anomaly, $\theta(t)$. We first solve for $E(t)$ in Eq.(2.38), and plug the

⁸The motivation for rewriting Eq.(2.29) in this way is primarily to remain consistent with Eastman et al.’s (2013) notation.

⁹Following the notation in Eastman et al. (2013)

result into 2.39 to calculate $M(t)$. Finally we solve Eq.(2.40) for t , and plug in our result for $M(t)$:

$$E(t) = 2 \arctan \left[\sqrt{\frac{1-e}{1+e}} \tan \left(\frac{\theta(t)}{2} \right) \right] \Rightarrow \text{Eq. (2.39)} \Rightarrow t = \frac{P}{2\pi} M(t) + T_P \quad (2.41)$$

The program EXOFAST_GETMCMCSCALE can perform these conversion for any true anomaly. Of particular relevance to our conversation is the time of primary transit, T_C , which EXOFAST uses in lieu of T_P to parametrize the time stamp of each RV/transit data point (see Section 2.2.1.3 for more information). Following the convention established in Section 2.1.1 (that $\omega_* = \pi/2$ for circular orbits)¹⁰

$$\theta(T_C) = \pi/2 - \omega_* \quad (2.42)$$

2.2.1.3 RV Parametrization

Eastman et al. (2013) favor a RV parametrization given by $\log P$, $\log K$, T_C , $\sqrt{e} \cos \omega_*$, $\sqrt{e} \sin \omega_*$, γ , and $\dot{\gamma}$. I will briefly discuss the motivation for these choices. The motivation for $\log P$ and $\log K$ is simple: planets with periods or semi-amplitudes equal to zero are not physically possible. Recall from Section 2.1.1 that the angle of periastron is poorly defined for near-circular orbits. As a result, the *time* of periastron, T_P (generally usually used to parametrize time) will be poorly constrained, and change considerably from step to step, driving up the time needed to achieve convergence. As a solution, Ford (2006) suggested approximating the angular position of the star with respect to the XY plane (Section 2.1.1.1) at a given time, i.e., adding a constant to the angle of periastron that describes the angular position at a particular time in the orbit. Equation (2.42) has the required form, *and* describes the true anomaly of a very interesting time, T_C . Incidentally, possessing transit data for a given planet in the system will result in an improved constrain on the T_C prior. This is particularly relevant for EXOFAST, given its capability to fit

¹⁰See Eq.(11) in Eastman et al. (2013) for a complete list of interesting times in an orbit.

RV/transit data simultaneously. For all these reasons, Eastman et al. (2013) use T_C to parametrize the time stamp of the observation.

EXOFAST uses $\sqrt{e} \cos \omega_*$, $\sqrt{e} \sin \omega_*$ to parametrize e and ω_* . This non-linear option is about twice as efficient as the linear parametrization, and is easier to implement than other non-linear options (e.g., $e \cos \omega_*$, $e \sin \omega_*$). Lastly, it is worth mentioning that EXOFAST quotes the median values and 68 % confidence intervals for all parameters, including the eccentricity, known to have a bias against $e = 0$ (Lucy & Sweeney, 1971). Therefore, when using EXOFAST, one must inspect the e PDF carefully.

2.2.2 Combined RV/Transit Fit

One of the innovative features of EXOFAST is its ability to simultaneously fit transit and radial velocity data (Eastman et al., 2013), which has important statistical and scientific implications. While both models remain unchanged, the redundancy in constrained parameters between the two separate fits improves the quality of the combined fit, thereby allowing us to understand the system more holistically. In addition, the simultaneous RV/transit fit obtains the covariances between both models' parameters, thereby removing any assumptions about independence between parameters. This simultaneous fit feature becomes even more exciting when thinking about MINERVA's capability of obtaining high cadence radial velocities *and* photometric data for a given target.¹¹

The combined RV/transit parametrization, along with the mass and radius of the star (M_* and R_*), allow EXOFAST to solve for the parameters of a planetary system precisely. To constrain $\log g_*$, EXOFAST uses Torres et al.'s (2010) empirical polynomial relation between the masses and radii of the stars, their $\log g_*$, effective temperatures, T_{eff} , and metallicities, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Since the empirical relation can be calculated efficiently, EXOFAST defines $\log g_*$, T_{eff} , and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ as stepping parameters. Therefore, at each step of the chain, EXOFAST derives M_* and R_* values, and quantifies the difference between these and the

¹¹For a thorough description of how EXOFAST parametrizes, models, and fits transit data, see Eastman et al. (2013), Section 4.

Torres relation. To a larger difference corresponds a larger χ^2 penalty, which disfavors the step. Eastman et al. (2013) point out several limitations to – and consequences of – using the Torres relation in order to obtain self-consistent M_* and R_* priors. Firstly, the Torres relation is reliable on the regime of single (post-) main sequence stars with masses above $0.6 M_\odot$, and therefore so is EXOFAST. Relatedly, it is worth pointing out that Eastman et al. (2013) assume that the M_* and R_* derived from the Torres stellar model are independent. In Chapter 3, we explain how the most up-to-date version of EXOFAST – namely EXOFASTv2 – addresses these and other limitations.

2.2.3 Using EXOFAST

While the full DEMC version of EXOFAST is available as an IDL package that requires installation, one can get an intuitive understanding of how to use the code by visiting EXOFAST’s online interface.¹² This is precisely what I did in order to learn how to use the software before migrating to the command line, using a walkthrough RV/transit fit for HAT-P-3b that uses data from Torres et al. (2007).¹³ Nonetheless, this section is primarily intended to contrast §3.2.1.2, where I analyzed 55 Cnc using a newer version of the code that is exclusively ran through the command line. Therefore, this section contains a brief explanation of how to use EXOFAST through the command line in order to fit RV data.

We must begin by formatting the RV data file in three space-delimited columns `Time stamp (BJD_TDB)`, `RV (m/s)`, `RV Error (m/s)`. Since EXOFAST uses the Barycentric Julian Date (BJD) reference frame, and the Barycentric Dynamical Time (TDB) standard (§ 2.2.3.1), great care must be taken to identify the respective time stamp of the observations and convert them appropriately. EXOFAST uses functions for time conversion that rely on extensive libraries.¹⁴ As explained in §2.2.2, one must specify priors for $\log g_*$, T_{eff} , and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, which can either come in the form of spectroscopic priors or from

¹²<http://astrutils.astronomy.ohio-state.edu/exofast/exofast.shtml>

¹³<http://astrutils.astronomy.ohio-state.edu/exofast/example.html>

¹⁴A comprehensive list of available conversions is available in the “Time Utilities” section of the EXOFAST website <http://astrutils.astronomy.ohio-state.edu/time/>

www.exoplanets.org (Han et al., 2014). In the case of transit fitting, one must also specify the band in which the observation was taken (e.g. Sloan i'). All of the above information may be specified in one line within IDL:

```
EXOFAST,TRANPATH='hat3.flux',/NOSLOPE,/CIRCULAR, $
PRIORS=priors,BAND='Sloani', RVPATH='hat3.rv', $
PNAME='HAT-P-3b',MINP=2.85,MAXP=2.95
```

where TRANPATH and RVPATH specify the file names containing the data, the PRIORS input consists of a two-dimensional (2D) array containing prior values and their respective uncertainties, the BAND input specifies the band used for transit observations, and MINP,MAXP limit the range of the periods explored in the analysis (Eastman et al., 2013). The PNAME input calls for the case-insensitive name of the planet, as found in exoplanets.org, and may obtain spectroscopic priors from said website. The “backslash input” CIRCULAR assumes a circular orbit for the fit. A comprehensive list of these and more input options can be found on the EXOFAST website.

Upon running the above command, EXOFAST will fit the transit and/or RV data separately, scale their uncertainties separately, and then fit the combined data sets. The DE-MC process will then proceed as explained in §2.2.1.1, with useful status updates for the user. In particular, EXOFAST_DEMC prints the number of accepted steps and the maximum time until completion (assuming the maximum number of steps were to be taken). After taking 5% of the maximum number of steps allowed, the program will print whether the chains will be well-mixed by the time of completion. If such is not the case, it will recommend a conservative thinning factor (§2.2.1.1). For the purposes of this thesis, whenever EXOFAST recommends a thinning factor, we restart the fit with 2 to $4 \times N_{\text{THIN}}$.

Upon completion, EXOFAST outputs a host of publication-ready plots and tables, which we show and describe in Chapter 3 in the context of a newer version of this code. The generated plots include: (1) plots of the data, along with the best-fit model and residuals, (2) PDFs of each parameter, as well as covariance plots between all parameters,

and (3) a deluxe L^AT_EX table, which quotes the median values and 1σ uncertainties of the model parameters and other derived quantities.

2.2.3.1 A Note on Reference Frames & Time Standards

Exoplanet science relies heavily on the precision with which astrophysical events are measured, i.e., in how accurate the time stamp of a given observation is. Two components define any given time stamp: the reference frame and time standard. While the reference frame refers to the geometric location where one measures time, the time standard describes how any given clock ticks, and what its arbitrary zero point is. Despite their central importance, Eastman et al. (2010) found that there is serious ambiguity in the literature regarding the time standards adopted, to the extent that these go regularly unreported.

If one were to measure the same (suitable) astronomical event using a regular clock on Earth over the course of a year, its occurrence time could change by as much as 16.6 minutes.¹⁵ In order to correct for this effect, astronomers generally measure time with respect to the Sun, i.e. using the Heliocentric Julian Date (HJD). However, the Solar System (SS) planets exert a tug on the Earth that may introduce reference frame errors in the order of 8 seconds. A better option is the Barycentric Julian Date (BJD), which is measured with respect to the SS barycenter; as close as we can get to a non-accelerating reference frame. It is often the case that publications will report Julian Date (JD) as the reference frame of the observations, resulting in a lack of clarity regarding whether HJD, BJD or other JD-based metric was used.

In addition, the time standard of an observation informs how much we should trust our time stamp, regardless of the reference frame of choice. There are three well-known time standards: (1) Universal time (UT1), which is defined by length of the mean solar day, and changes depending of the position of the Earth in its orbit (reason for which it is rarely used is astronomy); (2) Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), is based on an average of atomic

¹⁵This is a result of the finite speed of light: $2 \text{ AU}/c = 16.6 \text{ min}$.

clocks but is not allowed to differ from UT1 by more than 0.9 s. Thus, we add a leap second to UTC every eighteen months (on average), rendering this time standard discontinuous.¹⁶ A better choice is (3) the Barycentric Dynamical Time (TDB), which accounts for different clocks ticking at different times, depending on how fast they are moving. This standard defines a truly uniform time.¹⁷ For the reasons outlined above, Eastman et al. (2013) explicitly require that input times stamps be reported using the BJD reference frame and the TDB time standard. In Chapter 3, I took great care to pinpoint the specific reference frame and time standard used for each set of observations, to the extent of contacting the first authors of relevant publications when necessary. However, I was not always successful at pinpointing the convention used.

2.2.3.2 More Features & Some Shortcomings

Throughout Section 2.2, I have presented a cohesive, yet incomplete picture of all the features that EXOFAST offers. Fortunately, my adviser and his co-authors have taken great care to document their IDL package in the EXOFAST website. In addition, this website contains online tools (e.g., Ephemerides calculator, Quadratic Limb Darkening code) to compliment the analysis. For all its wonders, EXOFAST can only fit single-planet systems. In the search for a sixth planet in the 55 Cancri system, which is the subject of the next chapter, I describe and use a new version of EXOFAST – EXOFASTv2 – capable of fitting multi-planetary systems.

¹⁶Just as BJD and HJD are often reported as JD, UT1 and UTC are often reported as UT. Therefore, we have yet another source of ambiguity to be careful about.

¹⁷Cool fact: These atomic clocks define 1 s to be equivalent to “9,192,631,770 periods of the radiation corresponding to the transition between the two hyperfine levels of the ground state of the caesium 133 atom” Eastman et al. (2010).

Chapter 3

SEARCHING FOR 55 CNC G

3.1 The 55 Cancri System

55 Cancri is one of the richest and most complex planetary systems ever discovered. It consists of a wide visual binary harboring five known planets of remarkable diversity. A K0-type dwarf, 55 Cancri A, is orbited by an M-dwarf ($V \approx 13$), 55 Cancri B, at a projected separation of ~ 1065 AU (Mugrauer et al., 2006). 55 Cancri A (55 Cnc hereafter) also hosts the five known planets, with masses ranging from $\sim 8M_{\oplus}$ to $\sim 4M_J$, and orbital periods spanning between ~ 0.7 days and 14 years. The system owes its roots to one of the early Doppler surveys, the Lick-Carnegie Exoplanet Survey (LCES). Indeed, the first eight years of Doppler measurements from the LCES led to the discovery of 55 Cnc b (Butler et al., 1997), a $\sim 4M_J$ planet on a ~ 14 day orbit and one of the first few exoplanets ever detected.

The RV time series from Butler et al. (1997) exhibited additional trends hinting at the presence of other orbiting bodies, likely with planetary masses. Indeed, Doppler measurements up to 2002 led to the discovery of 55 Cnc c and d, with orbital periods of 44.3 days and 5360 days, respectively (Marcy et al., 2002). In 2004, McArthur et al. used measurements from the Hobby-Eberly Telescope and the ELODIE spectrometer (OHP) to uncover an additional 2.8 day signal of a $17M_{\oplus}$ planet.¹ Nonetheless, Dawson & Fabrycky (2010)

¹At the time, 55 Cnc e was thought to be one of the first three Neptune-mass planets ever discovered,

showed that the 2.8 day signal was in fact an alias, and the more likely period for 55 Cnc e was 0.7365 days. The shorter period raised the planet’s transit probability to $\sim 25\%$, prompting follow-up characterization – using *MOST* (Winn et al., 2011) and warm *Spitzer* (Demory et al., 2011) – which confirmed the prediction.

In 2008, Fischer et al. (2008) found a fifth planet using 18 years of Doppler shift measurements obtained with Lick (250 binned velocities spanning from 1989 to 2007), and Keck (70 binned velocities acquired between 2002 to 2007). The five-planet fit had a $(\chi^2)^{1/2} = 1.67$, and an rms scatter of 6.74 m s^{-1} , slightly larger than expected from internal errors, stellar jitter, and instrumental effects. Although the excess scatter could be attributed to an underestimation of the above uncertainties, Fischer et al. (2008) also explored the possibility of a sixth planet in the system. Although they found no significant signals in the periodogram of the five-planet residuals (Fig. 3.1), Fischer et al. (2008) also assessed the detectability of a hypothetical sixth planet in the system with a period between 300 and 4000 days. They found that for orbital periods of 300 – 850 days, a sixth planet with an $M \sin i \lesssim 50M_{\oplus}$ would have resulted in a periodogram peak $< 50\%$ above the noise floor of Fig. 3.1, thereby eluding detection. By the same metric, a sixth planet with $M \sin i \lesssim 100M_{\oplus}$ and a period of 850 – 1500 days, or with $M \sin i \lesssim 250M_{\oplus}$ and a period of 1750 – 4000 days, could have eluded detection. In addition, they found that a sixth planet in mean motion resonance (MMR) would be particularly capable of avoiding detection.

Shortly after the discovery of 55 Cnc f, Raymond et al. (2008) mapped the stability of the orbital space in the large gap between planets f ($P \sim 260$ days) and d ($P \sim 14$ yr), using a hypothetical sixth planet g with a radial velocity amplitude of 5 m s^{-1} , and a mass of 0.5 – 1.2 Saturn masses. They found a large stable zone extending from 0.9 to 3.8 AU at eccentricities below 0.4. Figure 3.2 shows the stable zone, as well as the host of MMRs studied by Raymond et al. (2008). For example, Raymond et al. (2008) found

along with the planets orbiting GJ 436 (Butler et al., 2004; Maness et al., 2007), and μ Arae (Santos et al., 2004). 55 Cnc also became the first system known to contain four planets.

Figure 3.1: From Fischer et al. (2008) – Periodogram of the velocity residuals to a Keplerian model that contains the five planets. Velocities from both Lick and Keck were included in this analysis. No other compelling periods – representative of a sixth planet – are apparent.

that the 3g:1d MMR could contain a resonant planet in a strongly confined region between $a_g = 2.86 - 2.89$ AU.

The most recent RV studies of 55 Cnc (Endl et al., 2012; Nelson et al., 2014) have not found significant signals which could confirm the presence of a sixth planet in the system. Endl et al. (2012) used nearly 700 PRVs from the McDonald Observatory, Keck, Lick, and HJST to obtain a five-planet Keplerian orbital solution of 55 Cnc. Nelson et al. (2014) applied a DE-MC algorithm that incorporates N-body integration to fit 1418 RV data points from four observatories (Lick, Keck, HET, HJST). While neither of them found convincing evidence for a sixth planet in the system, Endl et al. (2012) hinted at the possibility of finding additional planets with more data. Figure 3.3 shows the respective periodograms of their residuals.

Besides serving as a probe for the diversity of exoplanets in the Universe, and offering a test for the effects of binary companions on the architecture and dynamics of planetary

Figure 3.2: From Raymond et al. (2008) – Stable zone between planets f and d, where stability is quantified as “Fraction of Time on Detected orbits (FTD)”, or the probability of detecting planets b through f on their current orbits given perturbations from a hypothetical planet g. Thus, the white areas represent simulated orbital regions that were stable for 10 Myr. Black regions were unstable.

systems (e.g., Eggenberger et al., 2004; Raghavan et al., 2006), the 55 Cancri planetary system has informed theoretical investigations pertaining to the composition, orbital evolution, and migration of exoplanets. Some exciting examples include the study by Kley et al. (2004) which found evidence in favor of the migration of planets b and c to their current locations – in lieu of in-situ formation–, and the confirmation by Endl et al. (2012) & Madhusudhan (2012) that 55 Cnc e is a solid, carbon-rich planet unlike anything we see in our Solar System.² The complexities of analyzing this system are only increased by the number of parameters required to model it, and the 25 yr span of observations available to characterize it (1989-2014). For all these reasons, I thought of 55 Cancri as the perfect candidate to test EXOFASTv2, and continue to explore the scientific question of whether there is indeed a sixth planet in the system. In this chapter, I present an updated study of the planets orbiting 55 Cancri A, using 1602 high-precision radial velocity measurements from five observatories, including the latest data release of the LCES HIRES/Keck Precision Radial Velocity Exoplanet Survey (Butler et al., 2017). To our knowledge, this fit uses

²This discovery was particularly exciting for public media outlets, who dubbed 55 Cnc e of being a “diamond planet” (e.g., <http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2012/10/11/diamond-planet-55-cancri-e>).

(a) From Endl et al. (2012) – Lomb-Scargle periodogram made with 663 RV residuals of a Keplerian 5-planet fit. There are no significant signals above the noise level which could indicate the presence of additional planets in the system.

(b) From Nelson et al. (2014) – Periodograms made with 1418 RV residuals of a Keplerian 5-planet fit. The upper plot (Case 1) stems from a RV fit which assumes that all RV errors are uncorrelated. The lower plot (Case 2) stems from a RV fit which assumes that the measurement errors of observations taken within 10 minutes from each other are perfectly correlated (see Nelson et al. (2014) for more details.) There are no significant signals above the noise level.

Figure 3.3: Lomb-Scargle periodograms from two recent RV studies of 55 Cnc.

more data points than any other study in the literature. Section 3.1.2 reviews the stellar properties of 55 Cancri A. Section 3.2 summarizes the EXOFASTv2 methodology used in order to fit the multi-planet system. I describe the Doppler observations used, and present our results for each of the 55 Cancri planets, in Section 3.3. I conclude by highlighting the significance of our results, and offering a glimpse into the future of MINERVA and EXOFAST.

3.1.1 A Note on Choosing 55 Cancri

As part of the original goals for this thesis, I planned to include MINERVA data in the derivation of the RV model for a planetary system of my choice. In this way, I could have tested MINERVA’s 1 m s^{-1} RV precision, and perhaps could have demonstrated some of the benefits of using a high-cadence telescope array. Thus, one of the criteria for choosing 55 Cnc was its observability from Mt. Hopkins, AZ, between 2016 November and 2017 January. Ultimately, delays in the fiber installation (§1.3.1), and mechanical damages incurred by the Aqawans (§1.3.2) prevented us from incorporating MINERVA RV data in the subsequent analysis. Nonetheless, the prospect of obtaining MINERVA RV data for this system is now not only exciting, but also possible.

3.1.2 Properties of 55 Cancri

The star 55 Cancri A (= HD 75732 = ρ^1 Cnc A = HR 3522 = HIP 43587) is located in the constellation of Cancer, has coordinates RA = $8^{\text{h}}52^{\text{m}}36^{\text{s}}.13$, DEC = $28^{\circ}19'53.00''$, apparent brightness $V = 5.95 \pm 0.05$ and absolute visual magnitude $M_V = 5.47$.³ Its parallax, given by the new *Hipparcos* reduction (van Leeuwen, 2007), is of 81.03 ± 0.75 mas, corresponding to a distance of ~ 13 pc, or ~ 40 lyr. Based on improved interferometry, von Braun et al. (2011) derived $T_{\text{eff}} = 5196 \pm 24$ K, $R_* = 0.943 \pm 0.010 R_{\odot}$ and $L_* = 0.582 L_{\odot}$. Using isochrone fitting, von Braun et al. (2011) also report a best-fit age of 10.2 ± 2.5 Gyr, and

³SIMBAD Data Base, (Wenger et al., 2000).

a stellar mass of $0.905 \pm 0.015 M_{\odot}$ for 55 Cancri A. Valenti & Fischer (2005) found the stellar metallicity to be $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.315 \pm 0.03$, which places 55 Cnc in the fifth metallicity percentile of stars within 25 pc of the Solar System. von Braun et al. (2011) also derived $\log g = 4.45 \pm 0.01$, and $v \sin i = 2.46 \pm 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, which agree with previous results from Valenti & Fischer (2005). von Braun et al.’s values for T_{eff} , $\log g$ and $v \sin i$, as well as Valenti & Fischer’s $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ value, make up the priors for the original RV fits carried out throughout this chapter (§3.2).

3.2 EXOFASTv2

The second version of EXOFAST – EXOFASTv2 – is a powerful IDL software software capable of simultaneously fitting RV and transit data for multi-planetary systems (Eastman et al., in prep). Adviser Jason Eastman is the author of this software. While EXOFASTv2 is still in the beta testing stage, it is already available to the public as a GitHub repository.

3.2.1 Methodology: In Comparison with EXOFAST

When it comes to finding the best-fit parameters and calculating their uncertainties, EXOFASTv2 follows a similar methodology to its predecessor. Namely, it uses an analogous parameterization to restrict the region of explored parameter space near the global minimum (see Section 3.2.1.1), and the same debugged IDL AMOEBA code to hone in on the local minimum (§ 1.4.1, 2.2.1). EXOFASTv2 also uses ter Braak’s (2006) DE-MC process to step through parameter space and report confidence intervals, as well as the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to determine which links to accept. The code calls EXOFAST_GETMCMCSCALE to determine individual parameter deviates for the DE-MC process, consistent with Eq.(2.35). In order to determine whether the chains are well-mixed, EXOFASTv2 also requires that $T_z > 1000$ and $\hat{R}_z < 1.01$ for each parameter. Lastly, the code defines the “burn-in”, and suggests N_{THIN} factors, as prescribed in § 2.2.1.1.

3.2.1.1 Modeling & Parametrization

EXOFASTv2 describes the gravitational interaction between the host star and its planets as a sum of the form

$$RV(t) = \left[\sum_{n=0}^{n_p-1} K_n [\cos(\theta_n(t) + \omega_{*,n}) + e_n \cos \omega_{*,n}] \right] + \gamma + \dot{\gamma}(t - t_0) \quad (3.1)$$

where n_p corresponds to the number of planets in the system, and $\theta_n(t)$, e_n are the true anomaly and eccentricity for the n^{th} planet, respectively. Lastly, K_n corresponds to the radial velocity semi-amplitude of the n^{th} planet, given by

$$K = \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P(M_* + M_{P,n})^2} \right)^{1/3} \frac{M_{P,n} \sin i_n}{\sqrt{1 - e_n^2}} \quad (3.2)$$

The similarity between Eq.(2.36) and Eq.(3.1) evidences the form in which EXOFASTv2 fits multiple-planet systems: as a sum of Keplerian solutions to the two-body problem (§ 2.1.1). Thus, our solution ignores non-Keplerian gravitational interactions, and tidal effects. However, the modularity with which EXOFASTv2 is written may allow for these considerations to be incorporated into future data reduction pipelines. As discussed below, EXOFASTv2 is also capable of simultaneously fitting data sets from different telescopes, i.e., data sets with different systemic velocity offsets, γ , and different RV jitter values, σ_J . Since the same γ will be added to each data point from a given telescope, these are not expressed as a sum, but rather as shifting constants per RV data point. Although EXOFASTv2 is also capable of performing simultaneous RV and transit fitting, this analysis only employs the former technique.

Seeing as the model for EXOFASTv2 is essentially a sum of solutions to the two-body problem, it is no surprise that it uses a similar parametrization to EXOFAST: $\log P_n$, $\log K_n$, $T_{C,n}$, $\sqrt{e_n} \cos \omega_{*,n}$, $\sqrt{e_n} \sin \omega_{*,n}$, γ_j , and $\dot{\gamma}_j$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots, n_p - 1$ and $j = 0, 1, \dots, n_{\text{tel}} - 1$.⁴

⁴Although n_{tel} is meant to represent the number of telescopes, sometimes one telescope may require that its data be divided into additional subsets. In such cases, j is given by the number of subsets, not the

Please refer to Section 2.2.1.2 for a discussion of the motivation behind this parameterization.

As explained in Section 2.2.2, the set of parameters that are optimized during a simultaneous RV/transit fit, along with M_* and R_* , constrain a planetary system precisely. The parameterization of choice for the mass and radius of the planet is $\log g_*$, which is not constrained from the transit or RV data. Whereas EXOFAST uses the Torres et al. (2010) polynomial relation to constrain $\log g_*$, and thereby derive self-consistent M_* and R_* values at every step of the Markov chain, EXOFASTv2 incorporates a Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) fit (Hauschildt et al., 1999) and an isochrone stellar-evolution (YY) fit (Yi et al., 2001) to constrain the aforementioned parameters. Specifically, EXOFASTv2 derives self-consistent M_* and R_* values at every step of the chain. Consequently, it compares the values predicted from the SED and YY fits, imposing a prior penalty to the χ^2 that is proportional to their difference.

3.2.1.2 Using EXOFASTv2

I began this analysis with a performance test run aimed at reproducing the results from Fischer et al. (2008), with the exception of 55Cnc e, for which the aim is to recreate the results of Dawson & Fabrycky (2010) & Nelson et al. (2014) (see Section 3.1 for details). In describing this test run, I explain how to use EXOFASTv2, and interpret its outputs.

The performance test-run used the 70 Keck and 250 Lick RVs from Fischer et al. (2008), published along with their paper. Since the data came from two different telescopes, I wrote them into two separate files (using the format from §2.2.3). It is important to note that Fischer et al. report JD as their reference frame, and do not report a time standard. It was unclear if the published times were in Geocentric, Heliocentric, or Barycentric Julian Date or what time standard was used. Therefore, I input the time stamps as they appear on the paper, assume they are in BJD_{TDB} , and note that the time stamps may be ambiguous by

number of telescopes used to obtain data. For example, the Keck and Lick data in this thesis are divided into two and five subsets, respectively (§3.3.1).

up to 8 minutes (Eastman et al., 2010). Ideally, the time stamps would be in BJD_{TDB} .

The next step is specifying the priors for our parameters. Writing a two-dimensional array in the command line – just like with EXOFAST – becomes intractable with the amount of parameters required to fit this 5-planet system. With this in mind, EXOFASTv2 reads off the prior values from a text file, “55cnc.priors”, which is passed to the program using the `priorfile` input. It is instructive to see a screen-shot of the text file in the emacs interface (Fig.3.5). As was hinted at above, the priors used for the planets are consistent with the results from Fischer et al. (2008). Specifically, the prior file specifies parameters P , T_P , e , & ω and $\log K$ for each of the known planets. Unlike EXOFAST, EXOFASTv2 incorporates a SED fit to determine the luminosity of the star and in-turn, the stellar radius. To generate this SED fit (Fig. 3.4), I inputted all known magnitudes of the system into a file called “55cnc.flux.txt”. The allowed filters are the Johnson U , B , V , J , H , D ; the second generation Sloan g' , r' , i' , z' ; and the Infrared WISE 1-3 filters. The flux values for 55 Cnc originate from van Belle & von Braun (2009), Ducati (2002), Monet et al. (2003), & (Cutri et al., 2003) compiled in the SIMBAD data base.

```

# Syntax is FILTER, mag, mag uncertainty
# See mag2fluxconv.pro for allowed filters
B      6.82 0.05
V      5.95 0.05
J2M    4.59 0.05
H2M    4.14 0.05
K2M    4.015 0.036
#WISE1 10.537 0.023
#WISE2 10.583 0.021
#WISE3 10.618 0.097
#uSDSS 7.45 0.05
#gSDSS 12.14652 0.03
rSDSS  5.4 0.03
iSDSS  5.0 0.03
#zSDSS 13.20863 0.03

```

Figure 3.4: Demonstration of appropriate syntax for an EXOFASTv2 flux file.

Having written the data, priors and flux information into separate text files, one can call EXOFASTv2 within IDL using one line of code:⁵

```
exofastv2, nplanets=5, rvpath='55cnc.*.rv', $
fluxfile='55cnc.flux.txt', prefix= '55cnc.test.', $
priorfile='55cnc.priors', fittran=[0,0,0,0,0], $
fitrv=[1,1,1,1,1], circular=[0,0,0,0,0], nthin=40, $
maxsteps=1d3, logfile='55cnc.log', /debug
```

where again, `rvpath` specifies the file name(s) containing the data,⁶ `fluxfile` specifies the file name containing the known visual magnitudes of the target, and `priorfile` specifies the file containing the priors. The file `prefix` is used to differentiate between output files of different test runs. The `fittran`, `fitrv`, and `circular` inputs are one-dimensional (1D) arrays on length `nplanets`, which specify whether (= 1) or not (= 0) to fit transits and/or radial velocities for a given planet, and assume circular orbits. In terms of planet indexing within these 1D arrays, EXOFASTv2 follows the chronological order of discovery (b-f in this case). I also specified the maximum number of steps allowed, `maxsteps`, and the thinning factor `nthin`. Given the sheer number of parameters, chains, links, and redundant copies of each that must be stored, it is relatively easy to reach the 2 GB limitation for single processes (e.g. IDL) ran in 32 bit operating systems (like the one used), especially with a system as complex as 55 Cnc. Indeed, when `maxsteps > 5000`, the fit required over 2 GB of memory in order to run to completion.⁷ This prompted us to insert a flag, which tells the EXOFASTv2 user how much RAM the fit will require *before* starting the AMOEBA fit.⁸

⁵Note that IDL is a case-insensitive language.

⁶Notice the use of the wildcard (*) in the `rvpath` input. As mentioned above, EXOFASTv2 can simultaneously fit data sets from different observatories, i.e., with different γ values. The wildcard guarantees that EXOFASTv2 collects the data from all relevant files. As is shown in Figure 3.5, for each telescope used, a different γ prior must be specified.

⁷The only way to work around this limitation is to use a 64-bit operating system. However, it is preferable to thin the chains instead of having to handle such a large volume of data

⁸In this way, the user may adjust `maxsteps` before letting the code run for days, only to fail tragically toward the end.

```

teff 5196 24 # effective temperature
feh 0.315 0.03 # metallicity
#age 1 -1
logg 4.450 0.01 #self-gravity
vsini 2460 500 #velocity
#av 0.15 0.30 #visual extinction
ma 5.95 0.05 #apparent magnitude in V band
#distance 247.87 57.223
parallax 81.03 0.75
gamma -20 -1 #for tel 0-Keck
gamma_1 -20 -1 #for tel 1-Lick
#
#sorted by chronological order
period_0 14.65162 -1
tp_0 2450002.94749 -1
e_0 0.014 -1
omegadeg_0 131.94 -1
logk_0 1.85321 -1
#
period_1 44.3446 -1
tp_1 2449989.3385 -1
e_1 0.086 -1
omegadeg_1 77.9 -1
logk_1 1.00775 -1
#
period_2 5218 -1
tp_2 2452500.6 -1
e_2 0.025 -1
omegadeg_2 181.3 -1
logk_2 1.67071 -1
#
period_3 0.736546 -1
tp_3 2455568.011 -1
e_3 0.0 -1
omegadeg_3 90 -1
logk_3 0.798651 -1

```

Figure 3.5: Demonstration of appropriate syntax for an EXOFASTv2 prior file.

Finally, one can specify an optional input `logfile` to write the terminal outputs onto a text file. Since EXOFASTv2 is still in the beta testing stage, the terminal log files are important for subsequent analysis and bug searching. Additionally, T_z and \hat{R}_z are printed on the terminal upon DE-MC completion, and I needed their values in order to quantify how well-mixed the chains are. Before starting a fit, I always ran the code using the optional `\debug` flag, which essentially plays a movie of the AMOEBA routine settling into the best fit, allowing us to inspect the data for outliers and anomalies (Fig. 3.6). As the name implies, this flag is intended for inspection and debugging *only*, seeing as plotting this process slows down the code by orders of magnitude.

Upon running the command above, EXOFASTv2 prints the starting values for all the step parameters and the AMOEBA stepping scale. Whenever priors are not specified within `55cnc.priors`, the code adopts a default guess. A parameter number is assigned at this stage, which is useful for tracking down unconstrained parameters, and debugging in general. The code then begins the AMOEBA fit, printing an upper bound for its duration (13.5

min in this case). Specifically, it fits the transit and RV data separately, as described in § 2.2.1.3, and then fits the combined data sets and their uncertainties. However, this entire analysis uses RV data only. EXOFASTv2 then determines the appropriate stepping scale (§ 2.2.1), and initiates the DE-MC process with twice as many chains as parameters, updating the user on the status of the code in the same manner as its predecessor (§ 2.2.3). During a prior run, after taking 5% of the maximum number of allowed steps, EXOFAST_DEMC suggested a thinning factor > 22 , reason for which I set it to 40 and restarted the code. The average step acceptance rate for the chain was $\sim 7.5\%$, considerably below the ideal 23% acceptance rate stated by Gelman et al. (2003), but still acceptable. For the performance run, the fitting process took ~ 18 hr in a 32 bit operating system computer.

Figure 3.6: The debug flag runs a movie of the AMOEBA fit, as it settles into the best-fit model for all the known planets.

3.2.1.3 Outputs & Validation

Upon completion, our test run outputs a host of plots and files, which include: (1) plots of the data, along with the best-fit model for each planet, which are shown in Figure 3.9; (2) PDFs of each parameter, a subset of which are shown in Figure 3.7 (3) a deluxe \LaTeX table, which quotes the median values and 1σ uncertainties of the model parameters and other derived quantities (Table 3.1).⁹ This table is automatically produced, thereby eliminating human error when transcribing best-fit parameter values for publication-style table formatting. In addition, the code generates a publication-ready SED curve, shown in Figure 3.8. An additional output is an array of steps populated by the Markov chain, which includes all derived quantities and χ^2 values at each step. This is meant to provide a complete record of the evolution of the chain.

With a $T_z > 3000$, and a $1.01 < \hat{R}_z < 1.1$ for all parameters, the performance test chains were certainly well-mixed. To quantify the level of agreement between the derived median parameter values and Fischer et al.’s, I employed the well-known Z -statistic of the form

$$Z = \frac{p_{i,\text{BF}} - p_{i,\text{F}}}{\sqrt{(n \sigma_{i,\text{BF}})^2 - (n \sigma_{i,\text{F}})^2}}$$

where $p_{i,\text{F}}$ represents the value for the i^{th} parameter derived by Fischer et al. (2008), $p_{i,\text{BF}}$ is the best-fit analog, and n is an integer value between 0.5 and 3. EXOFASTv2 does not assume Gaussian errors. Thus, when computing Z , I use the lower $\sigma_{i,\text{BF}}$ if $p_{i,\text{BF}} > p_{i,\text{F}}$, and the higher $\sigma_{i,\text{BF}}$ otherwise.

Generally, our results were in very good agreement with those found by Fischer et al. (2008), and Endl et al. (2012) in the case of 55 Cnc e (for $n = 0.5, 1, 2$). All the values listed in Table 3.1 were within 2σ of theirs, and a decisive majority were within 0.5σ . Some exceptions include the ω values for 55 Cnc d, e and f. This discrepancy stems from the use of a different arbitrary range. I.e., while Fischer et al. define ω_p from 0 to 2π ,

⁹EXOFASTv2 is also capable of generating covariance plots between all parameters. However, the large memory required to produce such plots prompted us to remove them from this thesis’s fits.

EXOFASTv2 defines ω_p in the $[-\pi, \pi]$ range. After adding 2π to the quoted values, and recalculating the Z-statistic, the discrepancy was solved. The most significant difference between the two RV fitting methods used lies in the determination of the stellar properties. While EXOFASTv2 uses an SED fit and an isochrone stellar-evolution (YY) fit (Yi et al., 2001) to derive self-consistent M_* and R_* values at every step of the chain, Fischer et al. (2008) fix the stellar mass to the average between estimates by Valenti & Fischer (2005) and Takeda et al. (2007), and report fractional errors in the derived planetary masses of 8% in addition to errors in their orbital parameters. Given that EXOFAST uses fundamentally different stellar property modeling methods subject to different systematic errors, it is no surprise that our $M_p \sin i$ values were not as consistent with those from Fischer et al. (2008) as the rest of the derived parameters. Despite being the most discrepant, these values are still within 2σ of the results from Fischer et al. (2008).

Figure 3.7: Demonstration of the PDFs outputted by EXOFASTv2. Within EXOFASTv2, the script EXOFAST_PLOTDIST generates the posteriors for all parameters, a subset of which is shown here. In general, these diagnostic plots are not intended for publication. Nonetheless, the non-Gaussian posteriors featured above demonstrate the importance of understanding the nature behind uncertainties beyond the 1σ values. For this reason, some authors (e.g., Nelson et al., 2014) are releasing their posterior samples along with their publications.

Figure 3.8: Publication-ready SED plot. The overlaid red circles represent the inputted magnitude values for the filters in `55cnc.flux.text`.

Figure 3.9: Demonstration of the RV curve output by EXOFASTv2. The plot shows separate best-fit RV curves for each of the known planets orbiting 55 Cnc. The black circles represent Keck data, and the green squares represent Lick data.

Table 3.1. Median values and 68% confidence interval for Performance Test Run

Parameter	Units	Values
Stellar Parameters:		
M_*	Mass (M_\odot)	$0.917^{+0.019}_{-0.018}$
R_*	Radius (R_\odot)	0.950 ± 0.012
ρ_*	Density (cgs)	$1.510^{+0.049}_{-0.047}$
$\log g$	Surface gravity (cgs)	$4.4451^{+0.0096}_{-0.0095}$
T_{eff}	Effective Temperature (K)	5212 ± 21
[Fe/H]	Metallicity	0.321 ± 0.030
L_*	Luminosity (L_\odot)	$0.598^{+0.019}_{-0.018}$
Age	Age (Gyr)	9.3 ± 1.3
A_v	V-band extinction	$0.027^{+0.037}_{-0.030}$
M_a	Apparent V-band Magnitude	$5.994^{+0.039}_{-0.038}$
M_b	Absolute V-band Magnitude	$5.512^{+0.038}_{-0.039}$
<i>Error scaling</i>	Error scaling	$9.7^{+3.9}_{-2.4}$
d	Distance (pc)	12.28 ± 0.11
π	Parallax (mas)	81.40 ± 0.72
Planetary Parameters:		
a	Semi-major axis (AU)	$0.1433^{+0.0094}_{-0.0024}$
P	Period (days)	14.65182 ± 0.00016
MP	Mass (M_E)	288^{+120}_{-27}
RP	Radius (R_E)	$9.8^{+1.0}_{-1.4}$
e	Eccentricity	$0.0107^{+0.0060}_{-0.0061}$
ω_*	Argument of Periastron (Degrees)	151^{+34}_{-33}
i	Inclination (Degrees)	63^{+18}_{-25}
		$0.2548^{+0.0078}_{-0.0050}$
		$44.3460^{+0.0096}_{-0.0096}$
		$63.6^{+34}_{-9.1}$
		$9.5^{+2.5}_{-1.7}$
		$0.035^{+0.036}_{-0.025}$
		93^{+76}_{-59}
		57^{+23}_{-24}
		$10.15^{+1.1}_{-0.40}$
		5212^{+58}_{-60}
		1330^{+600}_{-130}
		$5.00^{+0.53}_{-0.76}$
		0.030 ± 0.014
		-170^{+26}_{-20}
		63^{+16}_{-25}
		$0.01571^{+0.00017}_{-0.00012}$
		0.7365418 ± 0.0000048
		$9.9^{+8.5}_{-1.4}$
		$3.19^{+1.4}_{-0.62}$
		$0.101^{+0.073}_{-0.065}$
		168^{+37}_{-25}
		53^{+25}_{-28}
		$0.823^{+0.024}_{-0.019}$
		$260.15^{+0.71}_{-0.71}$
		$56.3^{+32}_{-9.2}$
		$8.8^{+2.5}_{-1.6}$
		$0.084^{+0.12}_{-0.060}$
		-169^{+89}_{-56}
		57^{+25}_{-25}

Table 3.1 (cont'd)

Parameter	Units	Values
ρ_P	Density (cgs).....	$1.68^{+2.1}_{-0.51}$
$\log g_P$	Surface gravity.....	$4.51^{+0.28}_{-0.12}$
T_{eq}	Equilibrium temperature (K).....	$646.2^{+7.5}_{-20}$
Θ	Safronov Number.....	$0.321^{+0.25}_{-0.053}$
$\langle F \rangle$	Incident Flux ($10^9 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$).....	$0.0395^{+0.0019}_{-0.0046}$
T_C	Time of Transit (BJD _{TDB}).....	2450001.244 ± 0.044
T_P	Time of Periastron (BJD _{TDB}).....	$2450003.7^{+1.4}_{-1.3}$
T_S	Time of eclipse (BJD _{TDB}).....	$2450008.493^{+0.040}_{-0.041}$
T_A	Time of Ascending Node (BJD _{TDB}).....	$2449997.563^{+0.039}_{-0.041}$
T_D	Time of Descending Node (BJD _{TDB}).....	$2450004.848^{+0.041}_{-0.042}$
K	RV semi-amplitude (m/s).....	$71.53^{+0.40}_{-0.424}$
$\log K$	Log of RV semi-amplitude.....	$1.8545^{+0.0024}_{-0.0025}$
$e \cos \omega_*$	-0.0081 ± 0.0061
$e \sin \omega_*$	$0.0041^{+0.0058}_{-0.0047}$
$M_P \sin i_*$	Minimum mass (M_E).....	$258.6^{+3.7}_{-3.7}$
M_P/M_* ..	Mass ratio.....	$0.000945^{+0.00040}_{-0.00088}$
R_P/R_* ..	Radius of planet in stellar radii.....	$0.0947^{+0.0099}_{-0.014}$
a/R_*	Semi-major axis in stellar radii.....	$32.50^{+0.67}_{-2.1}$
d/R_*	Separation at mid transit.....	$32.37^{+2.1}_{-2.1}$
b	Impact parameter.....	$14.3^{+12}_{-9.8}$
δ	Transit depth.....	$0.0090^{+0.0020}_{-0.0024}$
$Depth$	Flux decrement at mid transit.....	0.00
P_T	A priori non-grazing transit prob.....	$0.02784^{+0.00063}_{-0.0013}$
		$0.43^{+0.29}_{-0.16}$
		$3.91^{+0.12}_{-0.12}$
		$484.8^{+4.4}_{-7.3}$
		$0.140^{+0.039}_{-0.023}$
		$0.01249^{+0.00047}_{-0.00073}$
		$2449990.54^{+0.80}_{-0.81}$
		$2449991.3^{+9.5}_{-9.5}$
		2450012.68 ± 0.78
		$2449979.72^{+0.84}_{-0.81}$
		$2450001.32^{+0.75}_{-0.78}$
		10.24 ± 0.39
		$1.010^{+0.016}_{-0.017}$
		$-0.000^{+0.028}_{-0.029}$
		$0.016^{+0.039}_{-0.022}$
		$53.5^{+2.2}_{-2.1}$
		$0.000208^{+0.00011}_{-0.00030}$
		$0.092^{+0.017}_{-0.017}$
		$57.78^{+1.8}_{-2.2}$
		$56.9^{+2.4}_{-2.4}$
		30^{+12}_{-20}
		$0.0084^{+0.0050}_{-0.0028}$
		0.00
		$0.01600^{+0.00077}_{-0.00063}$
		$0.000411^{+0.000014}_{-0.000037}$
		$0.43^{+0.29}_{-0.16}$
		$3.91^{+0.12}_{-0.12}$
		$484.8^{+4.4}_{-7.3}$
		$0.140^{+0.039}_{-0.023}$
		$0.01249^{+0.00047}_{-0.00073}$
		$2449990.54^{+0.80}_{-0.81}$
		$2449991.3^{+9.5}_{-9.5}$
		2450012.68 ± 0.78
		$2449979.72^{+0.84}_{-0.81}$
		$2450001.32^{+0.75}_{-0.78}$
		10.24 ± 0.39
		$1.010^{+0.016}_{-0.017}$
		$-0.000^{+0.028}_{-0.029}$
		$0.016^{+0.039}_{-0.022}$
		$53.5^{+2.2}_{-2.1}$
		$0.000208^{+0.00011}_{-0.00030}$
		$0.092^{+0.017}_{-0.017}$
		$57.78^{+1.8}_{-2.2}$
		$56.9^{+2.4}_{-2.4}$
		30^{+12}_{-20}
		$0.0084^{+0.0050}_{-0.0028}$
		0.00
		$0.01600^{+0.00077}_{-0.00063}$
		$0.000411^{+0.000014}_{-0.000037}$
		58^{+77}_{-18}
		$5.76^{+0.30}_{-0.32}$
		$76.8^{+1.3}_{-3.9}$
		205^{+180}_{-37}
		$0.00000789^{+0.00000056}_{-0.0000015}$
		2451226^{+29}_{-30}
		2452620^{+280}_{-280}
		2453740^{+17}_{-17}
		24555082^{+37}_{-36}
		2452490^{+18}_{-17}
		46.45 ± 0.54
		$1.6669^{+0.0050}_{-0.0051}$
		$-0.028^{+0.015}_{-0.014}$
		$-0.0041^{+0.0094}_{-0.0097}$
		1192^{+24}_{-23}
		$0.00436^{+0.00020}_{-0.00094}$
		$0.0483^{+0.0022}_{-0.0074}$
		2300^{+74}_{-74}
		2311^{+250}_{-79}
		1020^{+990}_{-710}
		$0.002333^{+0.00053}_{-0.00066}$
		0.00
		$0.000411^{+0.000014}_{-0.000037}$
		$1.69^{+1.2}_{-0.73}$
		$4.04^{+0.12}_{-0.12}$
		1953^{+14}_{-15}
		$0.00403^{+0.0013}_{-0.00070}$
		$3.26^{+0.10}_{-0.12}$
		$2455568.020^{+0.025}_{-0.023}$
		$2455568.160^{+0.026}_{-0.022}$
		$2455568.349^{+0.027}_{-0.028}$
		$2455567.820^{+0.028}_{-0.025}$
		2455568.181 ± 0.021
		6.01 ± 0.38
		$0.779^{+0.027}_{-0.028}$
		$-0.081^{+0.070}_{-0.079}$
		$0.013^{+0.056}_{-0.045}$
		7.96 ± 0.51
		$0.0000324^{+0.000028}_{-0.000058}$
		$0.0308^{+0.0060}_{-0.0060}$
		$3.559^{+0.042}_{-0.042}$
		$3.48^{+0.17}_{-0.22}$
		$2.0^{+1.3}_{-1.3}$
		$0.00095^{+0.00099}_{-0.00034}$
		$0.00000^{+0.00060}_{-0.00060}$
		$0.278^{+0.019}_{-0.015}$
		$0.00488^{+0.000033}_{-0.000035}$
		$0.47^{+0.32}_{-0.17}$
		$3.92^{+0.14}_{-0.14}$
		$269.7^{+2.5}_{-3.9}$
		$0.428^{+0.12}_{-0.073}$
		$0.001180^{+0.000052}_{-0.000082}$
		2450016^{+14}_{-12}
		2450087^{+64}_{-64}
		2450137^{+10}_{-11}
		$2449945.7^{+9.5}_{-9.4}$
		$2450078.3^{+8.3}_{-8.4}$
		$5.01^{+0.41}_{-0.40}$
		$0.700^{+0.036}_{-0.036}$
		$-0.037^{+0.060}_{-0.15}$
		$-0.009^{+0.042}_{-0.056}$
		46.8 ± 3.8
		$0.000184^{+0.000011}_{-0.000030}$
		$0.085^{+0.016}_{-0.016}$
		$186.6^{+5.5}_{-3.0}$
		187 ± 11
		99^{+62}_{-67}
		$0.0073^{+0.00047}_{-0.00025}$
		0.00
		$0.00488^{+0.000033}_{-0.000035}$

Table 3.1 (cont'd)

Parameter	Units	Values
$P_{T,G}$	A priori transit prob	0.000454 ^{+0.000017} -0.000047
T_{FWHM}	FWHM duration (days)	0.00
τ	Ingress/egress duration (days)	0.0000 ^{+0.00019} -0.00
T_{14}	Total duration (days)	0.000 ^{+0.001} -0.00
b_S	Impact Parameter	2.1 ^{+1.2} -1.4
$T_{S,FWHM}$	FWHM duration (days)	1020 ⁺⁹⁸⁰ -710
τ_S	Ingress/egress duration (days)	0.000 ^{+0.049} -0.00
$T_{S,14}$	Total duration (days)	0.0000 ^{+0.0020} -0.00
P_S	A priori non-grazing eclipse prob	0.000 ^{+0.00014} -0.000017
$P_{S,G}$	A priori eclipse prob	0.000458 ^{+0.000048} -0.000000
Wavelength Parameters		
Telescope parameters		
γ	Instrumental offset (m/s)	17.33 ^{+0.62} -0.61
σ_J	RV Jitter	21.2 ^{+3.6} -2.9
		0.00580 ^{+0.00036} -0.00031
		0.00
		0.00
		0.00
		97 ⁺⁶⁰ -65
		0.00
		0.00
		0.00
		0.00
		0.270 ± 0.016
		0.289 ^{+0.016} -0.015
		0.00500 ^{+0.00039} -0.00034
		0.00593 ^{+0.00045} -0.00028

Note. — From left to right, planetary parameters are reported according to the order in which they were discovered (b-f).

3.3 Searching for 55 Cancri g

3.3.1 Observations

Having completed a successful performance test with EXOFASTv2, wherein the IDL package was capable of navigating the formidable parameter space ($> 7 \times$ number of planets), I proceeded to fit 1,602 RVs spanning 25 years (1989 – 2014) from five observatories: Lick, Keck, Hobby-Eberly Telescope (HET), Observatoire de Haute-Provence (OHP), and Harlan J. Smith Telescope (HJST) (Fig. 3.10). Notably, I used a new set of ~ 200 RVs from the most recent Keck/HIRES data release (Butler et al., 2017). I also obtained HET, HJST and un-binned Lick data sets through private communication with Dr. Benjamin Nelson (CIERA¹⁰), as well as binned ELODIE data (Naef et al., 2004) through private communication with Dr. Jennifer Burt (MIT). Although an online version of the Lick data was published along with the LCES 25-year data release paper (Fischer et al., 2014), those RVs are binned. Figure 3.10 provides additional information on each data set.

Making use of EXOFAST’s ability to fit different γ values (corresponding to RV offsets of different data sets), I emulated Nelson et al. (2014) to divide and label the Lick and Keck data sets. In particular, Fischer et al. (2014) explained that the use of different CCD Dewars for data acquisition on the Hamilton spectrograph (Lick) results in inconsistent RV zero-point offsets between data points. As a result, Nelson et al. (2014) divided the Lick data into five subsets, depending on which Dewar was being used at the time of observation. Fischer et al. (2014) associate a Dewar code to each data point. The Dewar codes are: 6, 8, 39, 18, and 24. Dewar code “6” has 5 observations ranging from $\text{JD} - 2440000 = 7578.7300$ to 8375.6692 ($\gamma_{1,Lick}$). Dewar code “8” has 12 observations ranging from $\text{JD} - 2440000 = 8646.0011$ to 9469.6478 ($\gamma_{2,Lick}$). These first data sets have relatively high jitter values. Thus, further RVs taken with Dewars 6 and 8 are separated into different subsets. Dewar code “39” (Dewar 13 in Fischer et al. (2014)) has 96 observations

¹⁰Center for Interdisciplinary and Exploratory Research in Astrophysics (CIERA) at Northwestern University

ranging from $\text{BJD}-2440000 = 9676.0632$ to 11298.722 ($\gamma_{3,Lick}$). Dewar code “18” (Dewar 6 in Fischer et al. (2014)) has 91 observations ranging from $\text{BJD}-2440000 = 11153.033$ to 12409.739 ($\gamma_{4,Lick}$). Dewar code “24” (Dewar 8 in Fischer et al. (2014)) has 378 observations ranging from $\text{BJD}-2440000 = 12267.957$ to 15603.809 ($\gamma_{5,Lick}$). Note that the time series of Dewars 39 and 18 overlap. Such is also the case with Dewars 18 and 24.

Nelson et al. (2014) also split the Keck dataset based on whether observations were taken before or after the CCD upgrade and new Doppler reduction process of 2004 (Butler et al., 2017). I adopted the same convention to divide the 629 Keck RVs. Specifically, there are 23 pre-CCD upgrade observations spanning from $\text{BJD}-2440000 = 12219.138044$ to 13077.041736 ($\gamma_{1,Keck}$), and 606 post-CCD upgrade observations ranging from $\text{BJD}-2440000 = 13339.043299$ to 16829.74508 ($\gamma_{2,Keck}$). Including the ELODIE, HET and HJST offsets – (γ_{ELODIE} , γ_{HET} and γ_{HJST}), respectively – our fit modeled ten RV offsets.¹¹

Telescope/ Spectrograph	No. of RV points	Span of Observations (BJD)	Span of Observations (Julian Year)	Reference Frame (reported)	Time Standard (assumed)	Originally Published by	Source (if not publication)	Notes
Keck/ HIRES	629 (unbinned)	2452219.13804 - 2456829.74508	2001 - 2014	BJD	UTC	Butler et al. (2017)		2 subsets: pre-2004 post-2004
Hobby-Eberly Telescope / HET HRS	131	2452927.9841 - 2453117.69786	2003 - 2004	BJD	UTC	McArthur et al. (2004)	Dr. Nelson (private communication)	
Observatoire de Haute-Provence / ELODIE	48	2450207.3325 - 2452778.3426	1996 - 2003	BJD	UTC	Naef et al. (2004)	Dr. Burt (private communication)	
Lick / Hamilton	582 (unbinned)	2448646.0011 - 2455603.809	1992 - 2011	BJD	UTC	Fischer et al. (2008, 2014)	Dr. Nelson (private communication)	5 subsets: divided based on CCD Dewar used
Harlan J. Smith Telescope / Robert G. Tull Coudé	212	2451326.62945 - 2456054.59763	1999 - 2012	BJD	UTC	Nelson et al. (2014)	Dr. Nelson (private communication)	

Figure 3.10: Description of all five data sets, including the span of observations for each, and the source I obtained each data set from.

3.3.2 Methods

I set up a full RV fit run on EXOFASTv2 – using 1602 RVs – as described in Section 3.2.1.2, using ten data subsets. As is explained below, I did not carry out BJD_{UTC} to

¹¹Dr. Jennifer Burt also gave us the only two 55 Cnc data points obtained with the Automated Planet Finder (APF), not included for obvious reasons.

BJD_{TDB} conversions, and instead used the time stamps as reported by their respective publishers (See Fig. 3.10 for a breakdown). Prior to starting the run described below, adviser Jason Eastman and I modified the code such that it would generate residual files for each subset. Each residual file contained three columns: time stamp, 5-planet-fit – observation, and RV error (m s⁻¹).

I fit the residuals for each subset using EXOFAST (command line version), as described in Section 2.2.3, with the ultimate goal of assessing whether there were signals suggestive of a sixth planet in the system. Prior to fitting the residuals, we modified the routine `exofast_lombscargle` such that it would generate a plot of χ^2 vs. Period (days) for the residuals.¹² Consistent with the fact that the data spans ~ 25 years, the residual fit is restricted to periods smaller than 10^5 days. Although the analysis did not exclude the sub-day regime, the periodogram shown in Fig. 3.11 excludes periods of < 1 day. This choice is consistent with Fischer et al. (2008) (Fig. 3.1), Endl et al. (2012) (Fig. 3.3a), & Nelson et al. (2014) (Fig. 3.3b). It is worth reminding the reader that EXOFAST requires an array of priors (and their uncertainties) in lieu of a prior text file. For this reason, I wrote a short IDL script to define the prior array, using the best-fit values (and uncertainties) for $\log g_*$, T_{eff} , and γ_{tel} from the 5-planet RV fit. The remaining (uninformative) priors were set to zero (and their uncertainties to infinity, as instructed in the EXOFAST website). Upon running EXOFAST, the software printed a list of best peaks in the RV fit, along with their respective periods and χ^2_{ν} , onto the terminal.

3.3.3 Results

I used EXOFASTv2 to model 1602 RV observations spanning ~ 25 yr. With a $1500 < T_z < 1508$, and a $1.01 < \hat{R}_z < 1.04$ for all parameters, the chains of the 5-planet RV fit were well-mixed, such that I could use their residuals to search for a potential sixth-

¹²Although the χ^2 vs. Period (days) plot is not exactly a periodogram showing false-alarm probability of detection, it conveys similar information. For that reason, hereafter χ^2 vs. Period (days) plots are referred to as “periodograms”.

planet signal. All our values agree with those of Fischer et al. (2008) within 2σ , and a vast majority are within 1σ . Section 3.3.4 summarizes potential causes for the discrepancies in the context of planet d. The residuals from the five-planet RV fit had a $(\chi^2)^{1/2} = 3.84$, and an rms scatter of 6.87 m s^{-1} . Figure 3.15 shows the best-fit RV curves for the 5-planet fit, plotted along with the 1602 RV data points. Table 3.4 lists the derived estimates for all of the planetary parameters, and Table 3.2 shows the derived zero-point offsets and jitter estimates corresponding to the ten data sets.

I used EXOFAST to fit the residuals of the Keplerian 5-planet model and generate their periodogram (in the case of EXOFASTv2, a plot of χ^2 vs. Period (days)). Figure 3.11 shows the residual periodogram, from where I identified a significant signal at $P = 1736_{-15}^{+16}$ days with $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.092$, and four other somewhat less significant peaks in regions associated with common time sampling aliases, i.e., near one month and one year. Specifically, EXOFAST reported three monthly aliases ($P = 29.062206$ days, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.200$; $P = 25.000071$ days, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.169$; $P = 25.000079$ days, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.169$), and a yearly alias ($P = 363.008768$ days, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.165$). The RV fit of the residuals had a $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.08$.

Given the pervasive ambiguity in the 55 Cnc literature regarding the time standard used to report time stamps, I originally carried out two separate 5-planet and residual fits – one converting the time stamps from BJD_{UTC} to BJD_{TDB} , and one using them as reported by their respective publishers. I inspected the residual periodogram for each case in order to compare the strength of their respective monthly and yearly aliases. The converted time stamp residuals had stronger peaks (smaller $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2}$ values) near these aliases (e.g., $P = 25.008027$ days, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 2.844$; $P = 374.981911$ days, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 2.859$). Since a larger $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2}$ implies a weaker fit to the monthly and yearly aliases (which is desired), I discarded the converted residual periodogram. Therefore, to reiterate: *all the values reported in this analysis correspond to the 5-planet and residual fit using unconverted time stamps*. Figure 3.12 shows a RV fit of the residuals, and Table 3.3 summarizes the derived estimates for a

hypothetical sixth planet in the system which would be consistent with a ~ 1736 day signal. In the following section, I describe possible causes of the ~ 1736 day signal, and discuss future work that must be done in order to confirm or reject whether this could in fact be 55 Cancri g.

3.3.4 Discussion

The residuals from the five-planet RV fit had an rms scatter of 6.87 m s^{-1} , which is slightly larger than the analogous rms scatter of 6.74 m s^{-1} derived by Fischer et al. (2008) (F08, hereafter). I also found $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.84$, which is two times as large as the value reported by F08, $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 1.67$. Although the rms scatter of 6.87 m s^{-1} may be attributed to instrumental errors of the five telescopes (Fig. 3.10) and stellar jitter in the order of $1 - 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, the fact that our $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2}$ is twice that of F08 suggests that the 1602 RVs are less consistent with a 5-planet Keplerian fit. This may be due to additional systematic errors in the data that we are not yet aware of, which would not be surprising considering that I included data from five observatories, spanning ~ 25 years (7 years longer than the 320 Keck+Lick RVs used by F08). Since the larger $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2}$ implies a worse fit to the data, it could also indicate that there are additional planets in the system.

All the stellar and planetary parameters derived for the 5-planet Keplerian fit (except for planet d) agree with the results from F08 within 2σ , and are listed in Table 3.4. However, the majority of stellar parameter estimates have very tight uncertainties that are unlikely to be real (e.g., $M_* = 0.917_{0.019}^{+0.018} M_\odot$, $T_{\text{eff}} = 5212 \pm 21$, $\log g = 4.4452_{0.0095}^{+0.0096}$). This tight uncertainties stem from my use of extremely constraining priors for T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ (Valenti & Fischer, 2005; von Braun et al., 2011). In particular, multiple studies (e.g., Casagrande et al., 2006) have led to the understanding that certain parameters have systemic error floors. For example, T_{eff} and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ should have uncertainty estimates of at least 50 K and 0.08 dex, respectively. The tight uncertainties in stellar parameters likely propagated to the derived $M_p \sin i$ values, which partially explains why two of the

derived minimum planetary masses (for planets d and e) are barely within 2σ of the F08 results. Future work should use less constraining priors, which take systematic errors floors into consideration, in order to obtain more accurate error measurements for the stellar parameters and the minimum masses of 55 Cnc planets.

In addition to deriving stellar and planetary parameters for 55 Cnc, EXOFASTv2 also estimates instrumental offsets (γ) and RV jitter values (σ_J) for each of the ten data subsets (Table. 3.2). The instrumental offset estimates for data sets for HJST, HET, and Lick, agree with the values derived by Nelson et al. (2014) within 2σ . Our instrumental offset estimates for both Keck data sets differ from Nelson et al.’s by up to 4σ . This difference likely stems from the fact that this analysis uses ~ 200 additional Keck RVs spanning ~ 3 more years.¹³ It is likely that instrumental offset drifts over long time scales are contributing to this discrepancy. The RV zero-point offset for ELODIE is not included in this comparison since Nelson et al. do not use said data set. The derived σ_J values reported in Table 3.4 reflect how much each data set constrains the 5-planet fit, with the smallest RV jitter ($\sigma_J = 13.9 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) corresponding to the most numerous data set ($C_{2,Keck}$, 606 Rvs).

Having fit the 5-planet Keplerian model to 1602 RV data points, I also fit their residuals with the ultimate goal of assessing whether there were signals suggestive of a sixth planet in the system. A plot of χ^2 vs. Period (Figure 3.11) shows a significant signal at $P = 1736_{-15}^{+16}$ days, which could correspond to a hypothetical sixth planet with $K = 3.12_{-0.25}^{+0.28} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $M_P \sin i = 0.166_{-0.011}^{+0.012} M_J$, and $a = 2.795_{-0.018}^{+0.019} \text{ AU}$ (Fig. 3.12, Table 3.3). The RV fit of the residuals had a $(\chi_\nu^2)^{1/2} = 3.08$, which might mean that there are unaccounted-for systematic errors in this analysis, additional planet(s) in the system, and/or underestimated stellar jitter values. A discussion of these three possibilities follows.

The “two-tier” approach used in this analysis, whereby I fit and remove the five known planets before searching for a sixth, effectively assumes that we know the planetary pa-

¹³Whereas Nelson et al. used Keck data up to BJD–2440000 = 15728.743727 (2011 June), we use Keck data up to BJD–2440000 = 16829.74508 (2014 June).

Table 3.2. Estimates for the Instrumental Offsets, γ_j , and RV jitter values, $\sigma_{J,j}$, for the 5-planet RV fit.

Parameter (unit)	HJST	ELODIE	HET	Keck	Lick
$\gamma_{1,X}$ (m s ⁻¹)	-2.65 ± 0.57	15.0 ± 2.6	$0.45^{+0.99}_{-0.97}$	$-43.03^{+0.45}_{-0.47}$	-16 ± 11
$\gamma_{2,X}$ (m s ⁻¹)	—	—	—	-48.9 ± 1.4	-3.0 ± 4.9
$\gamma_{3,X}$ (m s ⁻¹)	—	—	—	—	$11.2^{+2.4}_{-2.2}$
$\gamma_{4,X}$ (m s ⁻¹)	—	—	—	—	-5.3 ± 1.2
$\gamma_{5,X}$ (m s ⁻¹)	—	—	—	—	-6.48 ± 0.56
$\sigma_{J,X1}$	$32.7^{+4.5}_{-4.0}$	164^{+56}_{-42}	$38.4^{+7.0}_{-5.8}$	$13.9^{+1.2}_{-1.1}$	320^{+1000}_{-250}
$\sigma_{J,X2}$	—	—	—	$33.2^{+15}_{-9.7}$	119^{+150}_{-74}
$\sigma_{J,X3}$	—	—	—	—	$50.0^{+11}_{-9.1}$
$\sigma_{J,X4}$	—	—	—	—	84^{+19}_{-16}
$\sigma_{J,X5}$	—	—	—	—	$56.9^{+5.2}_{-4.7}$

rameters of the system precisely, which is false. Therefore, all of the parameters of a hypothetical sixth planet that may be covariant with the planetary parameters of the five known planets (e.g., due to a MMR) have significantly underestimated uncertainties. In turn, tight planetary parameter uncertainties may systematically increase $(\chi^2_\nu)^{1/2}$. This scenario argues in favor of carrying out a global (6-planet fit) using EXOFASTv2, with priors for an additional planet informed by our derived hypothetical-planet parameters. This is left as an improvement for future work.

The studies carried out by F08 and Raymond et al. (2008) serve to argue in favor of the existence of the hypothetical sixth planet with a period of ~ 1736 days, a minimum mass of $\sim 0.166 M_J$ ($\approx 52M_\oplus \approx 0.55$ Saturn masses), and at a distance of ~ 2.795 AU from 55 Cnc A. With $P \sim 1736$ days, the hypothetical 55 Cnc g could be near a 3:1 MMR with planet d ($P_d = 5403^{+71}_{-65}$) days. Raymond et al. (2008) tested the long-term stability of 55 Cnc + an additional planet g with $M_P = 10M_\oplus, 30M_\oplus, 90M_\oplus$. They showed that, with a 3g:1d MMR, long-term stability (~ 10 Myr) would be achieved so long as planet g were located at $a_g = 2.86 - 2.89$ AU and had $e_g \leq 0.06$ (i.e., $e_g < e_d$) (Fig. 3.2). They also found that a smaller set of planets located between $a_g = 2.85 - 2.88$ AU, and with $e_g = 0.15 - 0.2$ could

Table 3.3. Median values and 68% confidence intervals for the planetary parameters of a hypothetical 55 Cnc g.

Parameter	Units	Value
Stellar Parameters:		
M_*	Mass (M_\odot)	$0.9665^{+0.0087}_{-0.0089}$
R_*	Radius (R_\odot)	$0.957^{+0.011}_{-0.012}$
L_*	Luminosity (L_\odot)	$0.607^{+0.021}_{-0.019}$
ρ_*	Density (cgs)	$1.559^{+0.054}_{-0.049}$
$\log(g_*)$	Surface gravity (cgs)	$4.4450^{+0.0094}_{-0.0092}$
T_{eff}	Effective temperature (K)	5213^{+19}_{-22}
[Fe/H]	Metallicity	$0.318^{+0.029}_{-0.027}$
Planetary Parameters:		
e	Eccentricity	$0.387^{+0.058}_{-0.059}$
ω_*	Argument of periastron (degrees)	$16.5^{+8.7}_{-9.1}$
P	Period (days)	1736^{+16}_{-15}
a	Semi-major axis (AU)	$2.795^{+0.019}_{-0.018}$
T_{eq}	Equilibrium Temperature (K)	$147.0^{+1.2}_{-1.1}$
$\langle F \rangle$	Incident flux ($10^9 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$0.0000917^{+0.0000044}_{-0.0000046}$
RV Parameters:		
$e \cos \omega_*$	$0.367^{+0.057}_{-0.059}$
$e \sin \omega_*$	$0.109^{+0.060}_{-0.061}$
T_P	Time of periastron (BJD _{TDB})	2455081^{+34}_{-36}
K	RV semi-amplitude (m/s)	$3.12^{+0.28}_{-0.25}$
$M_P \sin i$	Minimum mass (M_J)	$0.166^{+0.012}_{-0.011}$
M_P/M_*	Mass ratio	$0.000164^{+0.000012}_{-0.000011}$
γ	Systemic velocity (m/s)	-0.42 ± 0.25
$\dot{\gamma}$	RV slope (m/s/day)	$0.000276^{+0.000091}_{-0.000088}$
Primary Transit Parameters:		
T_C	Time of transit (BJD _{TDB})	2455252^{+26}_{-24}
T_{14}	Total duration (days)	$0.732^{+0.053}_{-0.048}$
$P_{T,G}$	A priori transit prob	$0.00207^{+0.00019}_{-0.00017}$
Secondary Eclipse Parameters:		
T_S	Time of eclipse (BJD _{TDB})	2454782^{+41}_{-39}
P_S	A priori non-grazing eclipse prob	$0.909^{+0.061}_{-0.057}$
$P_{S,G}$	A priori eclipse prob	$0.00167^{+0.00013}_{-0.00012}$

Figure 3.11: Periodogram of the 1602 RV residuals from the 5-planet Keplerian fit, showing a significant signal at $P = 1736^{+16}_{-15}$. A more thorough analysis is required to confirm or reject the presence of a sixth planet with such a period. The four additional red crosses, two of which overlap, most likely represent monthly and yearly time sampling aliases.

achieve long-term stability, but were observationally unlikely. Our signal corresponds to a hypothetical planet located outside this region ($a_g = 2.795^{+0.019}_{-0.018}$ AU), and with a larger eccentricity ($e_g = 0.387^{+0.058}_{-0.059}$). However, I reiterate that using this “two-tier” approach in the search for a hypothetical sixth-planet is likely to underestimate the uncertainties in planetary parameters. In the future, it would be worth exploring whether a global fit could inflate the parameter uncertainties, and allow for this hypothetical signal to be inside the stable region of the 3g:1d MMR. We also note that, moving slightly away from the 3g:1d region in Fig. 3.2, there appears to be room for a stable sixth planet with parameters that match our own. Considering that Raymond et al. (2008) restrict their analysis to MMR

Figure 3.12: RV Fit of the 5-planet model residuals – A hypothetical sixth planet with period $P = 1736^{+16}_{-15}$ would have a RV semi-amplitude $K = 3.12^{+0.28}_{-0.25}$ m s⁻¹, a scale which is also consistent with stellar activity cycles (Dumusque, 2012).

regions, and use 55 Cnc g masses that differ from that of our hypothetical planet, new dynamical stability analyses may yield promising results.

It is worth reiterating that neither Endl et al. (2012) nor Nelson et al. (2014) found a significant ~ 1736 day signal in their periodograms. This is especially suspicious in the case of Nelson et al. (2014), who only used about 200 less Keck RVs than I do in this analysis. As an additional exercise, I fit the 5-planet residuals using the Keck post-2004 subset only, for the converted and unconverted time stamps. Figure 3.13a shows that the strength of the ~ 1736 day signal significantly diminished in the case of the converted time stamps, matching the results from Nelson et al. (2014) (Fig. 3.3b). The variability of the signal with choice of time stamp suggests that the hypothetical sixth planet may

in fact be stellar jitter. This possibility is supported by the derived period and velocity semi-amplitude ($K \sim 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) for the signal (Table 3.3), which are consistent with stellar activity cycles for K-type stars (Dumusque, 2012). Going back to Table 3.4, some of the derived planetary parameters for 55 Cnc d differ from F08 by 2σ . E.g., the period estimate appears to have inflated (from 5218 ± 230 days (F08) to 5403_{-65}^{+71} days). Nonetheless, along the same line of reasoning one could argue that a 3g:1d MMR may be causing the inflation in 55 Cnc d parameter estimates.

Ultimately, a more thorough analysis is necessary in order to confirm or reject the hypothesis that this signal corresponds to 55 Cnc g. In order to improve the parameter and uncertainty estimates, and account for the potential covariance between 55 Cnc d and g, future work should include a global (six-planet) fit. In addition, false alarm probability tests should also be carried out to characterize significant signals, stellar jitter, and aliases more robustly. Considering the similarity between the results from Nelson et al. (2014) and Fig. 3.13a, future work must also revisit the choice of time stamp (converted or unconverted) for all the fits. Making use of the simultaneous fitting capabilities of EXOFASTv2, future analyses could include transit data for 55 Cnc e, which will result in better constraints on P_e , T_P , e , and the stellar parameters. Lastly, an N-body simulation including the hypothetical sixth planet can considerably enrich future analyses, as it could provide additional information on the long-term stability of a six-planet 55 Cnc. An exciting future awaits for this rich and complex system.

(a) Periodogram obtained using Keck data (post CCD upgrade). A one-year alias represents the deepest negative peak. The time stamps used to generate these residuals, and thereby this periodogram, were converted from JD_{UTC} to BJD_{TDB} . The strength of the signal at $P \sim 1736$ days diminishes, but is still apparent.

(b) Periodogram obtained using Keck data (post CCD upgrade), using the time stamps as reported by Butler et al. (2017) (BJD). The signal near 1736 days is still apparent above the noise level.

Figure 3.13: Discrepancy between periodograms using different time standards (of Keck post-2004 RV data only).

Data set	Symbol
Elodie	○
HJST	○
HET	●
Keck - pre 2004	▲
Keck - post 2004	★
Lick 1	□
Lick 2	○
Lick 3	▲
Lick 4	▼
Lick 5	★

Figure 3.14: Table describing the symbol and color used to plot each subset in the 5-planet 55 Cnc fit, seen in Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.15: Five-planet RV fit using 1,602 data points. This plot shows separate best-fit RV curves for each of the known planets orbiting 55 Cnc (b-f). The choice of phase in the x-axis allows for T_C to appear near $x = 0.25$. We represent Keck data in green, Lick data in blue, HJST data in red, ELODIE data as black unfilled circles, and HET data as black filled circles. Figure 3.14 details which symbol and color were used for each data subset.

Table 3.4. Median values and 68% confidence intervals for 55 Cnc using 10 data subsets.

Parameter	Units	Values
Stellar Parameters:		
M_*	Mass (M_\odot)	$0.917^{+0.018}_{-0.019}$
R_*	Radius (R_\odot)	0.950 ± 0.012
ρ_*	Density (cgs)	$1.511^{+0.049}_{-0.048}$
$\log g$	Surface gravity (cgs)	$4.4452^{+0.0096}_{-0.0095}$
T_{eff}	Effective Temperature (K)	5212 ± 21
[Fe/H]	Metallicity	$0.320^{+0.029}_{-0.030}$
L_*	Luminosity (L_\odot)	$0.598^{+0.019}_{-0.018}$
Age	Age (Gyr)	$9.3^{+1.4}_{-1.3}$
A_v	V-band extinction	$0.027^{+0.037}_{-0.020}$
M_a	Apparent V-band Magnitude	$5.994^{+0.039}_{-0.038}$
M_v	Absolute V-band Magnitude	$5.513^{+0.038}_{-0.039}$
Error scaling	Error scaling	$9.7^{+3.9}_{-2.3}$
d	Distance (pc)	12.28 ± 0.11
π	Parallax (mas)	81.41 ± 0.72
Planetary Parameters:		
a	Semi-major axis (AU)	$0.1431^{+0.0090}_{-0.0024}$
P	Period (days)	$14.651770^{+0.000070}_{-0.000071}$
M_P	Mass (M_E)	287^{+120}_{-74}
R_P	Radius (R_E)	$9.9^{+1.0}_{-1.4}$
e	Eccentricity	$0.0120^{+0.0029}_{-0.0030}$
ω_*	Argument of Periastron (Degrees)	160^{+13}_{-14}
i	Inclination (Degrees)	63^{+18}_{-24}
		$0.2546^{+0.0074}_{-0.0029}$
		44.4028 ± 0.0052
		61.7^{+33}_{-25}
		$9.4^{+1.7}_{-1.7}$
		$0.119^{+0.022}_{-0.023}$
		30.7 ± 9.2
		58^{+22}_{-25}
		$0.01571^{+0.00018}_{-0.00013}$
		0.73655500 ± 0.0000021
		$10.0^{+9.3}_{-1.7}$
		$3.22^{+1.5}_{-1.5}$
		$0.035^{+0.033}_{-0.024}$
		48^{+56}_{-63}
		53^{+25}_{-29}
		$10.16^{+1.0}_{-0.29}$
		5403^{+71}_{-65}
		1220^{+520}_{-150}
		$5.19^{+0.50}_{-0.76}$
		0.145 ± 0.010
		$-62.1^{+3.7}_{-4.1}$
		63^{+18}_{-25}
		$0.8208^{+0.025}_{-0.0094}$
		261.39 ± 0.22
		50.0^{+33}_{-29}
		$8.3^{+2.9}_{-1.5}$
		$0.526^{+0.044}_{-0.047}$
		$158.8^{+4.9}_{-5.2}$
		55^{+23}_{-26}

Table 3.4 (cont'd)

Parameter	Units	Values
ρ_P	Density (cgs)	48^{+58}
$\log g_P$	Surface gravity	$0.43^{+0.29}$ -0.16
T_{eq}	Equilibrium temperature (K)	$3.91^{+0.18}$ -0.12
Θ	Safronov Number	$484.9^{+1.3}$ -6.9
$\langle F \rangle$	Incident Flux ($10^9 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$0.138^{+0.037}$ -0.023
T_C	Time of Transit (BJD _{TDB})	$0.01235^{+0.00045}$ -0.00069
T_P	Time of Periastron (BJD _{TDB})	$2449984.80^{+0.64}$ -0.63
T_S	Time of eclipse (BJD _{TDB})	2449978.8 ± 1.2
T_A	Time of Ascending Node (BJD _{TDB})	$2449965.47^{+0.65}$ -0.66
T_D	Time of Descending Node (BJD _{TDB})	$2449975.86^{+0.60}$ -0.61
K	RV semi-amplitude (m/s)	$2449996.35^{+0.67}$ -0.66
$\log K$	Log of RV semi-amplitude	10.11 ± 0.20
$e \cos \omega_*$	$1.0046^{+0.0086}$ -0.0088
$e \sin \omega_*$	0.101 ± 0.022
$M_P \sin i$	0.060 ± 0.020
M_P/M_*	52.5 ± 1.3
R_P/R_*	Radius of planet in stellar radii	$0.000202^{+0.00011}$ -0.00027
a/R_*	Semi-major axis in stellar radii	$0.091^{+0.016}$ -0.014
d/R_*	Separation at mid transit	$32.48^{+2.0}$ -2.0
b	Impact parameter	$32.36^{+2.0}$ -0.67
δ	Transit depth	14.4^{+12} -9.8
$Depth$	Flux decrement at mid transit	$0.0090^{+0.0020}$ -0.0024
P_T	A priori non-grazing transit prob	0.00
		$0.01691^{+0.00065}$ -0.00096
		$0.00000771^{+0.0000054}$ -0.0000014
		$0.000000771^{+0.00000054}$ -0.00000014
		$0.00406^{+0.0014}$ -0.00072
		$3.294^{+0.086}$ -0.11
		$2455568.0248^{+0.0071}$ -0.0080
		$2455567.94^{+0.12}$ -0.12
		$2455567.6642^{+0.0079}$ -0.0069
		$2455567.8486^{+0.0083}$ -0.0077
		$2455568.2084^{+0.0077}$ -0.0093
		6.03 ± 0.19
		0.780 ± 0.014
		$0.014^{+0.030}$ -0.019
		$0.016^{+0.035}$ -0.020
		8.03 ± 0.28
		$0.000327^{+0.000031}$ -0.000057
		$0.0311^{+0.0061}$ -0.0061
		$3.560^{+0.043}$ -0.039
		$3.503^{+0.099}$ -0.13
		$2.1^{+1.4}$ -1.4
		$0.00097^{+0.0011}$ -0.00034
		$0.00000^{+0.00061}$ -0.00061
		0.00
		$0.2764^{+0.0073}$ -0.00076
		$0.000164^{+0.00011}$ -0.000026
		$0.080^{+0.015}$ -0.015
		$186.2^{+2.9}$ -2.9
		$113.6^{+10.}$ -8.9
		62^{+38} -42
		$0.0064^{+0.0048}$ -0.0022
		0.00
		$0.00807^{+0.00073}$ -0.00076

Chapter 4

Conclusion

Throughout this thesis, I used a “hardware-to-planet” approach in order to search for a sixth planet in the 55 Cnc system. By carrying out several instrumentation projects with MINERVA, I learned about the techniques that enable astronomers to use photons falling on the telescope primary to generate a raw spectrum of the observed star. By delving into the MINERVA Doppler pipeline, I improved my understanding of the forward modeling technique that allows MINERVA to model raw spectra, and extract Doppler shift measurements from them. By following Murray & Dermott (2000) & Seager et al. (2010) to re-derive the RV equation from first principles, I provided a description of how one can convert our observable, z , into a RV measurement. With the help of EXOFAST and EXOFASTv2, I used RV measurements of 55 Cnc to model its five known planets, and search for a sixth one. As Section 3.3.4 shows, substantial work remains in order to confirm the planetary nature of the identified ~ 1736 day signal. Nonetheless, the discovery of 55 Cnc g is an exciting prospect, and I look forward to continuing this search.

Following our repairs and fiber improvements, MINERVA is closer than ever to beginning its three-year RV survey. Therefore, the acquisition of original 55 Cnc data is a realistic prospect for the next observing season (between 2017 November and 2018 January). The high cadence and RV precision of MINERVA will prove valuable in acquiring

new 55 Cnc data (both RV and transit), although great care should be taken to plan a suitable observing strategy for this system. This is left for future work.

Once TESS launches, and begins monitoring over 200,000 main-sequence dwarf stars in the next few years (Ricker et al., 2015), there will be a higher demand for facilities dedicated to carrying out high-cadence RV follow-up of new exoplanets. There will also be a need for reliable and efficient software capable of generating both transit and RV curves. Thus, MINERVA and EXOFAST will prove extremely valuable as we carry on with the search for new worlds, especially considering their synergy.

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Chapter 5

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